

From Gender Bias to Textual Misogyny in the Early Modern Period: Bringing together Women's Writing from the Margins

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The perception of what constitutes a minor author or a minor genre, a great master or a great mind, has become increasingly problematic as gender comes into play and raises questions about the legitimacy of certain cultural assumptions and choices in our endeavour to ensure the visibility of women. Too often, as feminist practitioners, we are tasked with justifying why, then, not to focus on minor male figures when, for example, revising the curriculum. Why should the study of a so-called minor female thinker or artist should take precedence over her minor male counterparts - who might have enjoyed equal success in their own time? To this, this special issue on textual misogynies begins with premise of such interrogation requires careful consideration in an age where 'inclusion' has become an ethical as well as epistemic responsibility on the part of policy makers, knowledge producers (in both the education and heritage sectors), in an age where our relationship to cultural value has been entrenched within a gendered vision of the world and its history that tends to cultivate a dualistic approach to men's and women's creative potentials.

As the growing interest in early modern women's cultural, literary and political agency has shown over the last two decades, (re)writing history in the hands of feminist scholars is designed not merely to (re-)shape our collective memory and collective imaginary, but also to challenge deeply ingrained paradigms about knowledge production. Despite the recent advances in women's studies, current scholarship on early modern women perpetuates the enduring misrepresentations and mythification of women, as well as the near absence of tangible narratives about women's roles as political, cultural, artistic and literary agents, and, more broadly speaking, as producers of knowledge. These findings call for a transdisciplinary and transcultural re-assessment of how we shape foundational knowledge and of how new research in the Humanities and artistic practices can dialogue with each other to add important correctives to 'official' histories and standard feminist narratives.

With a focus mainly on how women born before the nineteenth century 'have acted out a role in history' and have been represented in the collective memory either by men or women, the chosen timeline of this volume's journey between past and present spans the Renaissance to the twenty-first century. This allows for a better understanding of the history of feminism from earlier manifestations within the long-centuries woman debates known as the *Querelle des femmes*, and of the impact of new feminist research, be it on school or university curricula, or on curated exhibitions and artistic creations. The chosen timescale, however, is not intended to replicate the conventional framework of periodisation which comes with inherently flawed categories of imposed knowledge. The notion of the early modern is here considered in its broadest sense with the aim to accommodate its conceptual and temporal fluidity in the transnational and transatlantic context of women's history from the Renaissance to Napoleon's memorable defeat in 1815. Although some of the women included here (Helen Maria Williams and the Sisters

Purbeck) were born in the middle of the 18th century and some of their most important works were published at the beginning of the nineteenth century, they were immersed in Georgian and Old Régime cultures while being, like Olympe de Gouges, key observers and participants in the formation of the political woman, albeit undermined by traditional historiography.

Yet, this discourse, this vision, articulated by politically minded women was in its infancy, then romanticised, and lost in 'translation' as these figures began to be excavated from the dusty bookshelves of national libraries and private collections. In the absence of women in the official history of Western society, feminist scholars have themselves been guilty of replicating androcentric readings of their foremothers' works. As the proposed issue seeks to demonstrate, the time has come to 'rebuild the practice of history', and thus destabilise the foundations of prevailing knowledge ordering systems. The objectives of this special issue are to reflect on how recovering women's past informs our own understanding of, and raises, questions about received methodologies across the Humanities, that is about epistemic responsibility. For example, how are the questions posed by philosophers different from questions posed by other disciplines in the Humanities? What is the relation between biography and philosophy, between biography and history of art, biography and the performative arts? By answering these questions, the contributors reflect on how our 'histories' of women (in philosophy, literature, history, the visual and performative arts) have been shaped by the discourses of their representation, and on how these discourses are challenged, and why those need challenging both within and beyond the confines of academia.

In their respective contributions, Catherine Power, Aurora Wolfgang, Sharon Nell, Oliva Smith, Francesca Blanch, Julia Lewandoswka, Lorenzo-Modia and Danila Sokolov challenge assumptions which, despite their disciplinary specificities, reveal and stress the importance of making these practices dialogue with each other across the disciplines. 'To advance knowledge-seeking and knowledge itself' by exploring various fields of academic enquiry, and not just correcting or filling the gaps, forms the *raison d'être* of this issue. By asking whether 'Virginia Woolf was wrong, and what else might have happened to Judith Shakespeare', Wolfgang revolutionizes the way we envision the project of feminist historical recovery and urges us to challenge 'the assumptions that structure our deepest beliefs about culture'. Rather than dismissing controversial monographs such as Shakespeare's *Dark Lady: Amelia Bassano Lanier the lady behind Shakespeare's plays* (2014) by John Hudson or *Sweet Swan of Avon: Did a woman write Shakespeare* (2011) by Robin P. Williams, her contribution takes these works and other similar ventures as thresholds into the uncharted waters of taxonomies, if not in the making yet, still unimagined. In other words, these should inspire us to think 'outside the box', to question the validity of the canon as we know it, and which has shaped our world vision from school textbooks to high and popular culture. As Nell argues, 'traditional academic models of periodization, genre and intellectual schools are increasingly awkward and inherently biased', and encourage repeating patterns of interpretation and representations which undermine women's cultural legacies. Far from being all-inclusive, the phrase 'cultural heritage' teems with potential for the recognition of women's contributions: gender-neutral in appearance, unlike the French term '*patrimoine*', it disguises centuries of ideological manipulation and indoctrination meant to condition how we read, interpret, tell and retell women's stories and lives. The official re-introduction of the potent phrase '*Journées du Matrimoine*' in France, in addition to the

conventional annual Heritage Day, thanks to academic and practitioner Aurore Evain, signals an important shift in the move towards sexual parity. Across the globe, the heritage sector has been working harder at making women more visible in museum and library exhibitions, even in magazines such as *Bazaar* that regularly features a section on a historical woman. Yet, even then, as the contributors warn us in the present issue, one must be wary of how we present this ‘matrimoine’ so as to avoid the traps of orthodox ideologies and enduring myths which cultivate dualistic interpretations opposing male and female, reason and intuition, logic and emotion, Smith’s article on feminist work in the history of popular philosophy puts forward a useful framework for re-evaluating how the epistemic space early modern women have carved for themselves has been reduced to a subjective set of paradigms, the private and the personal, which is in complete contradiction with the very practice of analytical philosophers. In a discipline where it is claimed arguments and their authors are distinct, it emerges that men’s and women’s texts are treated differently. Female philosophers’ texts (of which Mary Astell’s and Margaret Cavendish’s works are prime examples) are de-intellectualised, decoded through the lens of (auto) biographical records, such as labour and birth, or intimate relationships – denying those women a philosophical standpoint on a par with their male counterparts. Although it may be argued early modern women have had a better fate in literature and history departments, Smith argument resonates with the experiences of academics intent on disseminating knowledge about women’s contribution to our cultural heritage but often working in isolation. Sokolov perspective further testifies to the normative trends that have characterised the recovery of the history of women artists. For example, as he argues in his article, the life and work of artists like Mary Beale (1633-39), Sarah Hoadly (1676-1743), and Angelica Kauffman (1741-1807) were discussed in biographical collections such as Ellen Clayton’s publication *English Female Artists* (1867), and their works were (and were not) collected for national museums such as the National Portrait Gallery (founded 1856) or the National Gallery (founded 1838). How does one account for the (in)visibility women artists, and when they are made visible, how is the general public’s knowledge of these women’s works channelled? With Prado’s imminent bicentenary exhibition of Lavinia Fontana and Sofonisba Anguissola in mind, Sokolov gives first-hand insight into how the journey for the recognition of two major Renaissance female artists on a grand scale has much to reveal about the complex mechanics and gender politics of curatorial practices and about historians’ epistemological practice which Suzan Broomhall, in her ground-breaking research, has identified as ‘emotional historiography’. By investigating the historiographical practices that have characterised the formidably colourful afterlife of Catherine de Medici, Broomhall proposed a novel way of reflecting on how our historical encounters with other historical women of power have been shaped (whether these women are queens, intellectuals or artists).

Presented in a chronological and thematic order, the contributions in this issue all are new case studies ranging from the sixteenth to the eighteenth centuries. Francesca Blanch’s case study on Anna Seward provides another equally telling example of how the recovery of a female-authored work has not fully restored its author’s voice as an authority in late eighteenth-century political discourse. Seward held a central position in the literary landscape of the eighteenth century, and her advice and influence were sought after by her contemporaries. Her first publications, *Elegy on Captain Cook* (1780) and *Monody on Major André* (1781) were received with unparalleled enthusiasm by the reviewing press, who prophesied an auspicious future for her. Nevertheless, by the time of her death

in 1809, the reviewers' initial favour had declined, and the publication of the *Poetical Works of Anna Seward* (1810) and *Letters of Anna Seward* (1811) further ratified her critical devaluation. However, Seward claimed that if her verses possessed "the buoyant property of true poetry, their fame will be established in after years" and then, no one would ask "What said the reviewers?" (Seward 1811:4:203). Asking precisely that question, this article tackles the critical reception of Seward's works, analysing the variety of androcentric critical processes that interacted with—and were articulated by—Seward's reception by the press. New names keep emerging, and similar patterns of elision and obliteration recur as feminist scholars untiringly stitch newly excavated finds to the genealogy of women's feats in the production of knowledge. María Jesús Lorenzo-Modia's article on the Purbeck sisters, in its endeavour to 'dialogue with the literary tradition', further exemplifies the previous contributions' call for the need to persevere in destabilising paradigms and re-thinking how women writers interacted with their male peers, whether as scientists, historians or readers and interpreters of literature, or as socio-cultural agents and observers of political events. Like Seward and De Gouges, the Purbeck Sisters engaged, under the guise of fiction, with 'serious' topics, such as Jacobinism and anti-Jacobinism, and the ideology of the Terror Regime. The obscure(d) Purbeck Sisters are yet another example of how early modern women of letters cultivated virtue in the Aristotelian epistemic sense: through their intellectual interactions with political and scientific discourses, they positioned themselves as knowers, if not publicly, at least within the confines of their own inner rooms. As raised by Smith's, Lewandoska's and Wolfgang's case studies, one of the contentious points is how mainstream historiography with its misogynistic overtones has tended to represent, narrate and shape early modern women's intellectual lives, often reducing these to the biographical, to the personal, namely to the sensational. By and large, as many studies have shown in recent decades of feminist academic investigation, reading and interpreting their works have been informed by traditional modes of thinking. In other words, ideologically driven patterns of phallogentric fallacies have led to a subjective and flawed assessment of these women's works and contributions to the Arts and Humanities across time.

Biographies of these women have therefore become an objectionable source of reliable judgment: while the increase in studies focusing on near-forgotten female-authored works have become more and more valuable in the recovery of women's voices, biographies of women (whether by men or women) as a genre have only begun to re-surface as important documents for fully comprehending the narratives and counter-narratives that have influenced the representation of women across the disciplines represented in this issue.

Material culture in the last forty years has provided a framework for analysing a wealth of data regarding women's lives and works. The 'material turn', that is, the study of the relationship between authors and the actual production of their works (from printing to commercialization) was conceived in part as a scholarly interest in any aspect related to the business of writing that affected women's authorship and, thereby, scholars of women's literature have invoked it in many ways to enrich the scope of their inquiries. Nevertheless, it has contributed to reinforce the presence of women in the book and cultural market, often creating a confusion between object and subject, or between presence and impact. This blind spot affects our scholarship about women's writing across the European continent, since it tends towards a marginalization of thought whose participation in the marketplace was scarce or made irrelevant by dint of its perception as being "feminine".

The transition from manuscript to print in the sixteenth century, and women's gradual emancipation from patronage to market professionalization is proving a fruitful area of study due to the abundance of materials in library archives (especially from 1730-1890), including artefacts such as letters with editors or receipts on money received in exchange for writing for a market. However, the readings of these case studies tend to be biographical and historiographical, and focus on the repercussions of this professional emancipation of women for the history of gender.

Capturing the inner lives of historically famous women is however no easy task; too subjective a mission for the scholar, it has creative potential for novelists, poet and artists, but what of their voices? Making these women's voices heard not just on the page but also on stage is another venture which has yielded passionate, colourful, sensational portrayals of historical women, which still remain to be fully investigated. Theatre and performance studies have become essential to feminist historiographical work: interestingly, just as early modern women's lives have drawn the attention of historians, male and female alike, as Wolfgang and Nell have shown through their respective studies on libertine literature.

The 'experiential history' of women writing science allows us to explore the gendered language used by Maria Sibylla Merian's (male) contemporaries in their consideration and appraisal of her artistic and publishing achievements, particularly *Metamorphosis*. Although the vast majority of the commentary regarding Merian was positive, her artworks, publications, knowledge, and experience were almost uniformly and consistently diminished by the use of gendered language and omissions that suggested that she was less—less serious, less capable, less learned, less worthy—than a man. At the dawn of the eighteenth century in the Dutch Republic, the language of natural knowledge suggested that serious natural history was the province of men. Catherine Powell argues how the presentation of this seventeenth-century woman alongside a timeless alter ego creates a link between the present and the past that encourages a re-evaluation of women's roles then and now. In so doing, Powell highlights the crucial role the sciences are to play in the revival and promotion of historical women's voices beyond the confines of academia, in a way that resonates with other similarly riveting productions. Thus, while in her ivory boudoir Olympe de Gouges penned her 'imaginary' dialogues between Ninon de Lenclos and Queen Christina, Merian created a utopic vision of cultural sisterhood - a powerful counter-narrative for those who knowingly or not would follow in her footsteps. In Aurore Evain's words, 'to make women's legacies visible is to re-invent our relationship to History and to reinvigorate our cultural memory. Women are not limited to the status of biological mother, but they are also cultural and artistic mothers'. She had sensed the importance of creating an alternative story that defied mainstream ideology. Over the past months, while working on this issue, I have come to realise that the need to further the dialogue between academics and practitioners is ever urgent. It has become clear, indeed, that in order to not only retrieve but also to disseminate a more accurate, inclusive and vital history of women's past, we must engage in more creative and artistic encounters with our intellectual foremothers. Only in these interactions will we be able to break away from the prevailing stereotypes about women's roles and potentials; only then will the future of feminist ventures move forward.

**‘What experience does such a woman have?’
Maria Sibylla Merian (1647-1717) and the gendered language of
reception in natural history at the dawn of the Dutch eighteenth-century**

Catherine Powell

Abstract

“What experience does such a woman have after a short stay in a country such as Surinam...crawling about in forests and thickets...That is certainly no place for a woman.” This anonymous note concerned artist and naturalist Maria Sibylla Merian and her book *Metamorphosis Insectorum Surinamensium* (1705). The “experience” was not as banal as suggested; it consisted of an almost two-year, self-funded, exploration through Suriname, during which she collected, observed, and illustrated insects and their life cycles. Was the anonymous author’s strong reaction against Merian related to her gender, and was it unusual? This essay explores the gendered language used by Merian’s (male) contemporaries in their consideration and appraisal of her artistic and publishing achievements, particularly *Metamorphosis*. Although the vast majority of the commentary regarding Merian was positive, her artworks, publications, knowledge, and experience were almost uniformly and consistently diminished by the use of gendered language and omissions that suggested that she was less—less serious, less capable, less learned, less worthy— than a man. At the dawn of the eighteenth century in the Dutch Republic, the language of natural knowledge suggested that serious natural history was the province of men.

Keywords: early modern women and natural history; women and nature; early modern women writing for profit; women and the scientific revolution; gendered language and natural history

Introduction

What experience does such a woman have after a short stay in a country such as Surinam...crawling about in forests and thickets...That is certainly no place for a woman...¹

This anonymous manuscript, in the Artis Library at the University of Amsterdam, concerns artist and naturalist Maria Sibylla Merian (1647-1717). The book in question is Merian’s *Metamorphosis Insectorum Surinamensium* (1705). Her experience was not as banal as

¹ The author of this criticism was long believed to be Albertus Seba, a theory now in doubt. Hans Mulder has very recently compellingly argued against the likelihood of the author being Seba. Mulder has investigated the possibility that the author might have been someone in the circle of Levinus Vincent or Ottmar Elliger, amongst others, but concludes that it is simply not possible to determine with any level of certainty the identity of the author of the manuscript. The manuscript is difficult to access, but Mulder provides an image of it. Hans Mulder, *De Ontdekking van de Natuur* (Amsterdam: Terra, 2021), 136-140. The manuscript is also quoted and transcribed in Ella Reitsma and Sandrine A. Ulenberg, *Maria Sibylla Merian & dochters: vrouwenlevens tussen kunst en wetenschap* (Zwolle: Waanders, 2008), 242.

suggested: it consisted of a nearly two-year, self-funded, exploration through Suriname, during which Merian collected, observed, and illustrated insects, their life cycles, and their foods. Her field experience, in any event, exceeded that of many other male authors. Was the anonymous author's strong reaction against Merian related to her gender, and was it representative? (It could not have helped that, according to the author, Merian discarded the advice that he and the famous anatomist Frederik Ruysch gave her regarding the metamorphosis of a particular insect.)

This essay explores the gendered language used by Merian's (male) contemporaries in their consideration and appraisal of her artistic and publishing achievements, particularly *Metamorphosis*, an examination that has not taken place until now. In doing so, I begin with a brief consideration of the approach used by Merian herself in presenting her published works, which was very much attuned to the social expectations and reception she anticipated as a woman. I next assess comparatively the language used in the assessment of Merian and her work in contrast to that used regarding works painted and written by men. I consider the use of language in three broad categories of reception: reception by artistic commentators and theorists; reception by literary critics; and reception by learned men, principally affiliated with early modern scientific societies. I argue that although the vast majority of the commentary regarding Merian was positive, her artworks, publications, knowledge, and experience were almost uniformly and consistently diminished by the use of gendered language and omissions that suggested that she was less—less serious, less capable, less learned, less worthy— than a man. At the dawn of the eighteenth century in the Dutch Republic, the language of natural knowledge suggested that serious natural history was the province of men.²

² For a discussion of the association between nature and women, on the one hand, and domination, on the other, and the resulting marginalization of women in early modern science, see Carolyn Merchant, *The Death of Nature: Women, Ecology, and the Scientific Revolution* (New York: Harper & Row, 1980). Merchant revisits her arguments and offers valuable commentary in *Science and Nature: Past, Present, and Future* (New York; London: Routledge,

Maria Sibylla Merian: naturalist, artist, and writer

Maria Sibylla Merian was the daughter of the famous printmaker and publisher Matthäus Merian, who died when Merian was young. Merian received her artistic training from her stepfather, the still-life painter Jacob Marrel.³ Her true joy, according to Merian, seems to have been found in raising silk worms and caterpillars: to collect, observe, draw, dissect. Merian married her stepfather's apprentice, Johann Andreas Graff in 1665. The young couple moved to Nuremberg in 1670, where Merian began working on her watercolors of blooms and butterflies. It was in Nuremberg that she published a three-volume book series on flowers (plus one compilation volume) and the first volume of a two-volume series on caterpillars.

Merian appears not to have been happy in her marriage. In 1681, she returned to Frankfurt am Main with her daughters in order to comfort her mother after the death of Marrel. She would never return to live with her husband, although he did visit her on a few occasions in attempts to bring her back. In 1685, Merian, her two daughters, and her mother moved to the Dutch Republic and joined a Labadist religious community.⁴ Merian remained with the community until 1691, at which point she and her daughters (her mother having passed away)

2018). On the question of gender, sexuality, and nature, see Londa Schiebinger, *Nature's Body: Gender in the Making of Modern Science* (Boston: Beacon Press, 1993). In her examination of colonial literature related to silk production, Allison Margaret Bigelow conducts a different inter-textual analysis of the language used to describe silk work farming in the context of the development of a colonial economy that would engage women and indigenous people. She found that when male authors referred to women as the farmers of silk worms, the worms themselves became feminized through the use of pronouns. When the farmers were men, the worms were referred to in the masculine. Bigelow, "Gendered Language and the Science of Colonial Silk", *Early American Literature* 49 (2014), no. 2: 271-325.

³ There has been renewed interest in Merian scholarship over the past few decades. For a more recent biography of Merian, see Kim Todd, *Maria Sibylla Merian and the secrets of metamorphosis* (London: I.B. Tauris, 2007). Nathalie Zemon Davis, *Women on the Margins: Three Seventeenth-Century Lives* (Cambridge: Harvard University Press, 1997), remains highly relevant. Kurt Wettengl, Kurt (ed.), *Maria Sibylla Merian, 1647-1717: artist and naturalist* (Ostfildern-Ruit, Germany: Verlag Gerd Hatje, 1998), offers a comprehensive overview of Merian's body of work and includes reproductions of her letters to the German physician Johann Georg Volkamer and the English apothecary James Petiver.

⁴ The Labadists were a community of strict Protestants led by Jean de Labadie (1610-1674). For an overview of the movement and its founder, see Trevor Saxby, *The quest for the new Jerusalem, Jean de Labadie and the Labadists, 1610-1744* (Dordrecht: Nijhoff, 1987).

moved to Amsterdam. In Amsterdam, Merian and her daughters (whom she trained) operated a family workshop, creating and selling watercolors, almost exclusively under Merian's name.⁵

In 1699, Merian and her youngest daughter sailed for Paramaribo, Suriname. This was an exceptional journey to undertake for two women traveling alone.⁶ With the assistance of her daughter and slave plantation workers, Merian spent almost two years in the hot and humid jungle of Suriname collecting, nurturing, and observing insects and plants, and drawing and noting the results in her study book. In 1702, with Merian severely ill and the prospect of war between the Dutch and the French looming, the women returned to Amsterdam, where Merian died in 1717.

Between 1675 and 1771, there appeared at least nineteen editions of Merian's books.⁷ During the course of the eighteenth century, Merian's books were a "staple of the second-hand book trade".⁸

Merian's publications in her own words: not for my sake

Alone amongst Northern European women, Merian published a number of books on flowers, caterpillars, butterflies, and the other insects that captivated her. Although some women wrote technical books, particularly after the second half of the seventeenth century, these mostly fell into the category of "how-to" books and were generally intended for a female audience.⁹

⁵ Reitsma and Ulenberg explore the workings of the Merian family workshop in *Merian & Dochters*. The title appeared in English as *Maria Sibylla Merian and daughters. Women's lives between art and science* (Zwolle: Waanders, 2008).

⁶ Women who traveled to Latin America mostly began doing so in the late eighteenth and early nineteenth centuries. Adriana Méndez Rodenas, 'Women Travelers in Latin America: The Transatlantic Imagination', Special Issue: Literature and Arts of the Americas, *Women's Writing* 45 (2012), no. 1: 5-9.

⁷ Wettengl, *Maria Sibylla Merian*, 34.

⁸ Alicia C. Montoya and Rindert Jagersma, "Marketing Maria Sibylla Merian, 1720-1800: Book Auctions, Gender, and Reading Culture in the Dutch Republic", *Book History* 21 (2018): 63.

⁹ Based on searches in the Short Title Catalogue Netherlands (STCN). For a comparative perspective, see Elizabeth Tebeaux, "Women and Technical Writing, 1475-1700: Technology, literacy, and development of a genre", in Lynette Hunter and Sarah Hutton (eds.), *Women, Science and Medicine 1500-1700: Mothers and Sisters of the Royal Society* (Gloucestershire: Sutton Publishing, 1997), 29-62.

Noble women like Margaret Cavendish, Anne Conway, and Gabrielle Emilie du Châtelet wrote books on natural philosophy, chemistry, and even translated Newton's *Principia*. The German Maria Clara Eimmart published an illustrated work on the phases of the moon. Generally speaking however, publishing was not the norm for women, especially not in natural philosophy (a broad expression encompassing what we think of today as natural history, astronomy, chemistry, biology, physics, geology, and metallurgy).¹⁰ That women writers found themselves navigating a complex and fluid dichotomy between privacy and the cult of domesticity, on the one hand, and the public sphere and publicity, on the other, undoubtedly made female publication all the more fraught.¹¹

Merian's caterpillar books and *Metamorphosis* were addressed to a general public, based upon personal observation, and intended for the broad dissemination of natural knowledge. Merian inserted herself at the centre of the debates on insects of the time, including the question of spontaneous generation.¹² I am not aware of any other woman authoring a botanical treatise or coda in the Northern or Southern Netherlands or in the Germanies between 1600 and 1735.¹³ In his nineteenth-century expansive *History of the Natural Sciences*, George Cuvier refers only to one female author for the sixteenth and seventeenth centuries—Merian.¹⁴ From this perspective,

¹⁰ Sarah Hutton, "Science and Natural Philosophy", in Amanda Capern (ed.), *The Routledge History of Women in Early Modern Europe* (Oxford; New York: Routledge, 2020), 390-391.

¹¹ Martine van Elk, *Early Modern Women's Writing: Domesticity, Privacy, and the Public Sphere in England and the Dutch Republic* (Cham: Palgrave MacMillan/Springer Nature, 2017).

¹² Lizabeth Paravisini-Gebert, "Maria Sibylla Merian: The Dawn of Field Ecology in the Forests of Suriname, 1699-1701", Review: Literature and Arts of the Americas 45 (2012), no. 1: 10-20. On this question, see also Kay Etherington, *The Flowering of Ecology: Maria Sibylla Merian's Caterpillar Book* (Leiden; Boston: Brill 2021).

¹³ Elizabeth Blackwell's *A Curious Herbal containing five hundred cuts of the most useful plants, which are now used in the practice of physick, to which is added a short description of ye plants and their common uses in physick*, appeared in installments between 1737 and 1739 and is a very different book from Merian's.

¹⁴ George Cuvier, *Cuvier's History of the Natural Sciences: Nineteen lessons from the Sixteenth and Seventeenth Centuries*. New edition [online]. Paris: Publications scientifiques du Muséum, 2015 (generated 25 janvier 2021). DOI: <https://doi.org/10.4000/books.mnhn.2761>. Cuvier described *Metamorphosis* as having "magnificent" plates and being a work of luxury. He believed that the book had only appeared in 1719, after Merian's death.

as Natalie Zemon Davis remarked, “For the seventeenth century, Maria Sibylla Merian is a sample of one.”¹⁵

Merian’s first body of work, on flowers (*Blumenbuch*), appeared in three volumes over the course of five years, between 1675 and 1680.¹⁶ She published the three parts as a single tome as the *Neues Blumenbuch*, in 1680. These books represented Merian’s first foray into publishing. Unlike her other books, the flower books were intended for a female audience and focused on visual knowledge, making scant use of text, save in the 1680 compilation volume, which included a preface which provides clues regarding the intended audience. Merian specifically appeals to the role of educator ascribed to early modern married women, by appealing to the “young eager to learn”, and women’s craft and needlework.¹⁷

Merian (publishing under her married name, Gräffin) is also the author of a two-volume series on caterpillars and their “wondrous metamorphosis and extraordinary nourishment from flowers”, published in 1679 and 1683. As she had done with her books on flowers, Merian was careful to maintain her image as a modest, respectable woman, following what Carme Font Paz and Nina Geerdink have called the “rhetoric of modesty” that prevailed amongst early modern women writers.¹⁸ As noted by Martine van Elk, “While humanists acknowledged that women were spiritually equal to men and that there was a benefit to limited education for women, they

¹⁵ Davis, *Women on the Margins*, 155.

¹⁶ The Maria Sibylla Merian Society has helpfully compiled the list of Merian’s published works, together with a list (and many transcriptions) of primary sources on the artist and naturalist. (www.themariasibyllameriansociety.humanities.uva.nl)

¹⁷ For an introduction to the social gender expectations projected onto early modern women generally and in the Dutch Republic, see Elizabeth Storr Cohen and Margaret Reeves (eds.), *The youth of early modern women* (Amsterdam: Amsterdam University Press, 2018). Els Kloek, *Vrouw des huizes: een cultuurgeschiedenis van de Hollandse huisvrouw* (Amsterdam: Balans, 2010). Martha Moffitt Peacock, *Harpies, Heroines, and Housewives: Imaging Women of Consequence in the Dutch Golden Age* (Leiden: Brill, 2020). Although some of his assumptions and conclusions have been put into question recently (notably by Peacock), Simon Schama’s discussion of women in *Embarrassment of Riches* (New York: Vintage Books, 1987) remains highly informative.

¹⁸ Carme Font Paz and Nadine Geerdink, *Economic imperatives for women's writing in early modern Europe* (Leiden; Boston: Brill, 2018), 1.

also emphasized the need for women to remain within the household and display the traditional virtues of silence, chastity and obedience.”¹⁹ Not entirely consistent with her self-description as a “reluctant publisher”, however, Merian included a poem of praise of her work by Christoph Arnold (1627-1685), a teacher and deacon of a church in Nuremberg (I return to this poem below).

In proceeding with her quest to understand insects, Merian advises her reader that she was merely bearing witness to “God’s strange omnipotence” and “miraculous power” over small and insignificant insects, as so many had requested her to do. Merian takes great care in establishing herself as an observer and investigator of nature. In doing so, Merian signalled her dedication to empiricism, something which would have been of high importance to like-minded individuals in this period driven by what Brian Ogilvie has described as the “early modern European cult of fact”.²⁰

Metamorphosis

The achievement that brought the most attention to Merian was the publication in 1705 of *Metamorphosis Insectorum Surinamensium* (Transformations of the Insects of Suriname), the culmination of hers and Dorothea Maria’s dangerous and costly voyage.²¹ Merian and both daughters worked on the book. By then, Merian had been living separately from her husband for two decades or more; she was an independent woman with field experience. She had become Maria Sibylla Merian, naturalist and author. Her approach to the marketing of *Metamorphosis*,

¹⁹ Martine van Elk, “‘Blessed art thou, Reader, if you are not of that sex’: Public Femininity in the Seventeenth Century”, in Katlijne van der Stighelen et al. (eds.), *Michaelina Wautier, 1604-1689: Glorifying a Forgotten Talent* (Antwerp: Rubenshuis; Kontich: BAI, 2018), 123. In that essay, Martine van Elk suggests a compelling approach to the understanding of early modern women in the public sphere by describing three models of public femininity.

²⁰ Brian Ogilvie, *The Science of Describing: Natural History in Renaissance Europe* (Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2008), 12-13.

²¹ Kay Etherington argues that the caterpillar books represented a greater scientific achievement than *Metamorphosis*, notwithstanding the greater attention devoted to the latter. Etherington, *The Flowering of Ecology*, 109.

which she dedicated to “All nature lovers and investigators”, is more gender-neutral. Although the artistic achievement of *Metarmorphosis* was remarkable, art lovers were not her target this time. With this book, she set a high bar: to improve upon existing knowledge.²²

To openly challenge the work of respected amateur naturalists and learned experts, as she does in her Notice to Readers, was rather bold. Merian did, however, anticipate and attempt to neutralize her critics by projecting modesty in her self-representation (“they pressed me to share them in print, thinking this was the first and most remarkable work painted in America”); and by appealing to the economic necessity of the publication (“In making this work I have not sought to profit, and I will be satisfied to recover the expenses I have made”). Her strategy was not dissimilar to that employed by other contemporary female authors, as found for example by Geerdink in her examination of the early modern Dutch authors Maria Margaretha van Akerlaecken, Katharina Lescaijle, and Elisabeth Hoofman.²³

In this context, I argue that Merian’s reference to the collections of Witsen, Ruysch, and Vincent in her Notice to Readers was purposefully included to convey to her readers her familiarity with the best and most famous collections in Amsterdam, as well as with their owners. Put another way, Merian projected trustworthiness by association. She adopted the same strategy in the final lines of her Notice, in which she drops the names of some of the most respected, learned men, like Govert Bidloo, Thomas Moufet, and Jan Swammerdam. Merian concludes by saying that Caspar Commelin, M.D., director of the Amsterdam Hortus Medicus and inspector of the medical college, had provided the Latin descriptions for *Metamorphosis*.

²² In the Notice to Readers, she declared: “[...] in Holland I came to see with astonishment beautiful animals from East and West, ... but they lacked the origin and information about their generation, how they change from caterpillar to pupa [chrysalis] and so on; this has prompted me to undertake a large and costly trip, and to sail to Suriname in America”. Translations my own unless otherwise noted.

²³ Nina Geerdink, “Economic advancement and reputation strategies: Seventeenth-century Dutch women writing for profit”, *Renaissance Studies* 34 (2019), no. 3: 350-373. Nina Geerdink, “Possibilities of Patronage: The Dutch Poet Elisabeth Hoofman and Her German Patrons”, in Paz and Geerdink (eds.), *Economic Imperatives*, 124-146.

The suggestion being, implicitly, that Commelin approved Merian's work. This practice, which Leah Knight refers to as "social citation", serves as "a record of the community" that made Merian's work possible.²⁴ It legitimized her research in the eyes of a knowing public and anticipated critics who might suggest that, as a woman, the matters about which she wrote were beyond her grasp.

Reception to Merian and *Metamorphosis*: gendered language and omission

While Merian was careful to incorporate the practice of social citation into *Metamorphosis*, her male counterparts mostly failed to reciprocate, with two notable exceptions: the English apothecary James Petiver cites the two volumes of Merian's caterpillar books numerous times in his *Musei Pevieriani* of 1695; and the English botanist John Ray, in the epilogue to his *Historia Insectorum* of 1710, refers his readers to Merian's "elegantly engraved" insects in *Metamorphosis*.²⁵ The epilogue may have been added by Ray's editor, William Derham.²⁶ Even in these two instances, Merian does not receive the effusive treatment reserved for the other "learned" and "knowledgeable" (male) authors towards whom most writers feel deeply indebted.

Merian and her achievements, particularly her voyage to Suriname and *Metamorphosis*, attracted the attention of authors of artistic treatises and reference works, commentators in literary magazines, and even of the Royal Society in London. The reception of Merian and her achievements by these different groups is explored in turn, below. No commentator was as openly dismissive of Merian's work as the author who asked "What experience does such a

²⁴ Leah Knight, "Horticultural networking and sociable citation", in Anne Curry et al. (eds.), *Worlds of Natural History* (Cambridge 2018), 64.

²⁵ John Ray, *Historia insectorum opus posthumum jussu Regiae Societatis Londinensis editum* (London: Impensis A., and J. Churchill, 1710), 398.

²⁶ Etherington, *The Flowering of Ecology*, 28-29.

woman have”? Most commentators, to the contrary, praised Merian—in highly gendered terms, both explicitly and implicitly, in what Frederika H. Jacobs calls (albeit in another context) “problems of praise”: women could be heroines and, in these cases, should be celebrated. But virtuous women were, essentially, women who behaved like virtuous men. Thus, while gendered expectations did not necessarily bar a woman from a given field, gender almost always affected “critical assessments” of women’s professional activities.²⁷

Artistic reception: impressive—for a woman

Merian’s earliest printed praise coincided with the publication of her first flower book, in 1675. It was her fellow resident of Nuremberg, Joachim von Sandrart, who included her in his reference work *Teutsche Academie der Edlen-Bau-, Bild- und Mahlerey-Kunste*. Merian is part of the entry devoted to her husband: “Johann Andreas Graff...married to Maria Sibylla Merian, a graceful painter of flowers”, “daughter of the copper engraver Matthäus Merian”. Merian’s works, Sandrart notes “are most perfect to be replicated with the needle”. Merian has “prepared interesting lessons for the benefit of those who demand to learn and follow her virtues”. Furthermore, in addition to offering her virtues to the goddess Minerva, Sandrart writes, Merian performs “regular, good housekeeping”.²⁸

In the 1679 edition of the *Teutsche Academie*, Sandrart promotes Merian to “painter”, and allots her an entry under the name Maria Sibylla Graffin.²⁹ He notes that the artist was so well trained by her stepfather, Jacob Marrel, in the art of painting miniatures and flowers that she has attained perfection in this endeavour. This can be readily seen, he writes, in her book on

²⁷ Frederika H. Jacobs, *Defining the Renaissance Virtuosa: Women artists and the language of art history and criticism* (Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 1997), 9-10, 40-41.

²⁸ Joachim von Sandrart, *Teutsche Academie Teutsche Academie der edlen Bau-, Bild- und Mahlerey-Künste*, vol. II, book 3 (Nuremberg: Miltenberger, 1675), 339. Searchable version of the text: <http://ta.sandrart.net>

²⁹ Joachim von Sandrart, *Teutsche Academie der edlen Bau-, Bild- und Mahlerey-Künste*, vol. 3 (Nuremberg: Froberger, 1679), 85.

flowers, *Fasciculus Florum*, in which she was “excellently assisted by young [girls] through her teaching school” and which is “to be praised”, as several witnesses can attest.

In many ways, the language Sandrart employs, perhaps not surprisingly, echoes that used by Merian herself in marketing her books on flowers. There is more, however, to the use of language by Sandrart than simply (re)projecting her respectability and modesty. The reference to Merian’s capable housekeeping, for example, suggests a concern with Merian’s gender and her attendant duties, something which resounds even more given that Sandrart’s discussion of Merian is included under the entry allotted to her husband.

Sandrart’s 1679 entry is less overtly gendered. At first glance, his focus is on Merian’s abilities as an artist and on her observations of nature. A close reading, however, reveals that socially-constructed gender expectations continue to course through the text. Sandrart implies that Merian’s artistic skills are owed to her stepfather, who trained her expertly, and perhaps even due to her lineage as Matthäus Merian’s daughter. More glaring is the underhanded compliment regarding Merian’s book on flowers. Sandrart highlights that Merian assembled the book with the help of her young pupils, as part of their training by her. Readers would have known that Merian could not train young men to become professional artists, such a task being reserved for guild members.³⁰ The education she dispensed was of the nature appropriate for young women of well-to-do families who wished their daughters to receive a humanist education.³¹ Effectively, Sandrart reduced Merian’s empirical observations and skilful

³⁰ Nuremberg was a free imperial city. There was no guild. However, in order to practice a trade (such as painting) professionally, one needed approval of the City Council, which was constituted of the city’s founding regent families. This approval was not available to women. Dieter Wuttke, *Nuremberg: Focal Point of German Culture and History* (Bamberg: Kaiser, 1987). Rainer Brandl, “Art or Craft? Art and Artists in Medieval Nuremberg,” in Martin Angerer (ed.), *Gothic and Renaissance Art in Nuremberg* (Munich: Prestel 1986), 51-60.

³¹ For a recent overview of the educational opportunities available to women, see Peacock, *Harpies, Heroines, and Housewives*, 322-323, 329.

engravings to the work of an amateur blessed with good parentage, admirably instructing young girls in her spare time.

The use of gendered language is not unique to Sandrart. Merian's first caterpillar book, published in 1679, included a laudatory poem by Christoph Arnold. The poem appears before Merian's preface, thereby ensuring that this would be the first text readers perused. While Arnold's "song of praise" extolls Merian's skills, what he appears to find most astonishing is that Merian—as a woman— should undertake and successfully complete her observations and descriptions of caterpillars:

It is remarkable that a woman
Would dare to emulate
What the [male] scholars have accomplished.
[...]
But it is worthy of praise
That a woman should desire to do the same.
[...]
That an ingenious woman
Achieved all this, to while away her time.
[...]

Arnold mentions the greatest practitioners of natural history of the time (as well as Swammerdam, in a line not quoted here). In doing so, he elevates Merian's work to their standard. This praise, however, is diminished by Arnold's emphasis on Merian's gender, as it is by his note that her accomplishments were undertaken "to while away her time", meaning as a way to occupy herself when her household, wifely and motherly duties had been satisfied. We cannot know how Merian felt about her motherly and wifely duties, or whether she included these observations by Arnold in an attempt to pre-empt critics, to maintain her reputation, or to highlight what was important to her. It is fair to assume, however, that Merian approved of the language used by Arnold and it did not strike her as offensive or unusual.

Thus, although Sandrart and Arnold each recognize and celebrate Merian's skills as an artist, and as a naturalist (with a focus on her empirical observations), they insist on the significance of her gender, and on reassuring readers that her foremost duties, those related to her household, were not being neglected. Needless to say, no such assurances were required in the case of male artists.

Merian received more attention after the publication of *Metamorphosis*, in 1705. Arnold Houbraken devoted an extensive entry to Merian in the third volume of *de Grootte schourburgh der Nederlantsche konstschilders en schilderessen* (The Great Theatre of Dutch Painters), published in 1721, which he accompanied by her portrait.³² At the outset, Houbraken notes that Merian's aptitude for the arts was evident from the age of eleven, when she "tended more to the pencil than to domestic occupations". But "even with children and domestic worries", the "love of art continued to grow in her". About her work, he notes "Those who have browsed and read the work speak of it with great praise"—thereby distancing himself from the praise. He closes his entry on Merian with a poem, the last lines of which are as follows:

What gave her the joy, what gave her the desire?
She found entertainment in art, and in contemplation
The Creator the cause of all things.
Her name lives, though death hath quenched her light.

Houbraken clearly admired Merian. One cannot escape the conclusion, however, that for him Merian was *a woman* artist and naturalist. In his final analysis, Merian's art and observations of nature were for her entertainment and part of her devotion to God—not borne out of intellectual curiosity or from the desire to create and share knowledge.

³² Arnold Houbraken, *De Grootte schourburgh der Nederlantsche konstschilders en schilderessen*, Vol. 3 (Amsterdam: By the widow of the author, 1721), 220-224.

In contrast, when discussing the work of the painter Herman Saftleven, for example, Houbraken limits himself to discussing the quality of his work, which he believes was at its highest in the painter's middle period.³³ When discussing the painter Johannes Bronkhorst, Houbraken notes that he had been apprenticed to become a baker, which became his profession. However, his passion for art was so great that he learned how to paint, something he could do while continuing his work as a baker, remarked Houbraken. "He worked diligently in his spare time in art, and without any education got so far that he may be counted among the best artists in watercolor".³⁴ Houbraken does not tell the reader whether Bronkhorst's baking suffered as a result of his artistic pursuits.

I have chosen this intra-textual comparison between Merian, Saftleven, and Bronkhorst purposefully. Saftleven and Bronkhorst, like Merian, produced detailed, scientifically accurate illustrations of plants and insects, although only Merian published books with her engravings. All three artists received commissions from the patron and lauded amateur botanist Agnes Block to immortalize her rare and exotic plants, insects, and birds; and all three earned the admiration of Houbraken. Yet, Houbraken's approach to the memorialization of the artists is strikingly different in the case of the two men when compared to his approach to Merian, notwithstanding the relatively similar circumstances of their respective artistic production.

In 1730, Johann Gabriel Doppelmayr, in his *Historische Nachricht von den Nürnbergischen Mathematicis und Künstlern*, described Merian's pursuits of natural history as "quite eccentric", but admiringly described her findings in natural history as "completely new discoveries".³⁵ Doppelmayr continued to describe *Metamorphosis*, published in 1705, as "a

³³ Houbraken, *De Groote Schouburgh*, 340-342.

³⁴ Houbraken, *De Groote Schouburgh*, 242.

³⁵ Johann Gabriel Doppelmayr, *Historische Nachricht von den Nürnbergischen Mathematicis und Künstlern [...]* (Nuremberg: Monath, 1730), 268-269. <https://doi.org/10.11588/diglit.44011#0303>

precious work with 60 copper plates in Regal-folio, with many beautiful observations included in Dutch and, with the generous assistance of the learned Casp. Commelini, in Latin at the same time.” Doppelmayr was writing specifically to enhance the reputation of Nuremberg as a place where great artists and mathematicians flourished. Still, it is Caspar Commelin who receives his praise as learned: Merian had eccentric pursuits, completely new discoveries, and beautiful observations, but Commelin was a physician with Latin.

Literary reception: a woman (!) without precedent

At least two contemporary specialized literary magazines praised *Metamorphosis* soon after its publication. As was the case with artistic reference works, however, that praise was highly gendered. Willem Sewel, editor of the Dutch *De Boekzaal der Geleerde Werreld* (The Library of the Learned World), could barely contain his astonishment that Merian—a woman—should have undertaken a trip to Suriname and produced *Metamorphosis*:

[...] It is here, Reader, that I ask you to stop with me for a little while, so you can be amazed at the great eagerness to investigate and the immeasurable diligence of this Lady; it is not new for men to make great efforts in the pursuit of the wonders and rarities of Nature; the scholarly world has seen many such undertakings. But that a woman, who is already quite old, should undertake a trip to the West Indies, and out of *liefhebberij* decide to overlook the inconveniences of the heavy seas, the dangers of raging waves and roaring winds, only to investigate the reproduction of insects and to paint them closely after life, is something without precedent. [...] No expense has been spared in carrying out this excellent work; the plates were engraved by the most famous masters, and printed on the best and heaviest paper, to please connoisseurs of art as well as those who love insects and plants. [...] ³⁶

³⁶Willem Sewel, *De boekzaal der geleerde werreld voor de maanden ...*, Volume 1 (Amsterdam: Francois Halma, 1705): 91-99. The term *liefhebber* is usually translated as amateur, virtuoso, or lover of art. *Liefhebberij* is the term used to express the activities of the *liefhebber*, and include collecting, exploring, examining, investigating. For a lexicographical overview of Dutch seventeenth-century art historical sources that use the word *liefhebber*, see: <https://lexart.fr/terms/view/1843>. I am grateful to Dr. Claudia Swan for providing me with this reference.

Sewell goes on to provide a “brief sketch of the precise and praiseworthy work of our renowned artist”. The anonymous author of a review of *Metarmophosis* in the Leipzig-based *Acta Eruditorum*, in 1707, was similarly struck by Merian’s gender:

[Moufettus, Godart, May, Lister, Swammerdam and Blanckard] should be praised all the more as it could have seemed less attractive to write about lowly little animals that are mostly annoying and harmful to us. But who would believe that a woman would be attracted [to this subject] with such curiosity that she would collect insects with her own hands, paint them in vivid colors and engrave them in copper? Sparing no expense and unafraid of the danger threatened by a journey to America, a two-year stay in Surinam and the equally difficult return? Then again, she had already made an extraordinary name for herself before this, when she published the first part (1679) and then the most curious second part (1683) of *Observations on Insects*. But now with this work, which is definitely very beautiful, she deserves immortal fame among all the learned women who ever lived, because this book can undoubtedly compete with the efforts of the most famous craftsmen in this genre. Indeed among botanists as well she will henceforth be given a place of honor, because the foreign plants that she also depicts, as the insects’ food and quasi incidentally, thus far were either completely unknown or had been less accurately described by others...³⁷

It seems beyond question that the author admired Merian’s work. Indeed, the reference to the reception of Merian’s work amongst botanists and her characterisation as the *author* of the work (passage not cited here) are strikingly gender-neutral for the period. Nevertheless, it is amongst “learned women” that Merian should receive immortal fame, and not simply amongst learned individuals.

Metamorphosis was the only publication by a female to be reviewed in the 1705 *De Boekzaal der geleerde Werreld* and in the 1707 *Acta Eruditorum*, a fact from which we can infer the exceptional nature of Merian’s achievements. Arguably, however, her gender seems to have garnered as much attention as her work. Although she has gained admission to a male-dominated

³⁷ *Acta Eruditorum, publicata Lipsiae*, Calendis Novembris, Anno M DCC VII (November 1707), 481-482. Translation from the Latin by Dr. Corinna Vermeulen.

world, Merian is carefully kept aside, as an attraction of sorts but not as an equal to the many other self-taught male authors whose books are reviewed and recommended.

Specialist reception: the praiseworthy work of a *Curieuse* person

The anonymous author of the note that opens this essay said that Merian's caterpillar books were "insignificant", and that *Metamorphosis* amounted to "expensive prints".³⁸ It is difficult to imagine a more dismissive reception from a class of individuals that positioned itself at the top of the hierarchy of natural knowledge production, validation, and dissemination.

By the middle of the seventeenth century, the young discipline had become increasingly institutionalized.³⁹ Experiments and discussions moved away from the domestic space and into the scientific academies and universities. A lack of formal education (women in Northern Europe could not enroll in university), the impossibility of becoming a member of scientific academies (at least in London, Paris, St. Petersburg, and Vienna), and general lack of Latin, the universal tongue of scientific inquiry, effectively pushed early modern women to the periphery of the creation and dissemination of natural knowledge.⁴⁰

³⁸ Reitsma and Ulenberg, *Merian & Daughters*, 242.

³⁹ For an overview of the development of early modern natural history, see Brian Ogilvie's seminal *The Science of Describing*. For an exploration of the increased marginalization of women in early modern science, see amongst others Londa Schiebinger, *The Mind has no Sex? Women in the origins of modern science* (Cambridge: Harvard University Press, 1996).

⁴⁰ It was not until 1925 that the Royal Society (London) agreed that women could be admitted as members and a further twenty years before any women were in fact elected as such: Georgina Ferry, "The exception and the rule: women and the Royal society, 1945-2010", *Notes and records of the Royal Society of London* 64 (September 2010), no. 1: 163-172. It took the Académie des Sciences (known as the Académie Royale des Sciences until 1816) in Paris until 1979 to elect a woman: Schiebinger, *The Mind has no Sex*, 2. Women were accepted in several academies in Italy, however: Schiebinger, "Women of Natural Knowledge", in Katherine Park and Lorraine Daston (eds.), *The Cambridge history of science Volume 3: Early modern science* (Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2006), 197-198. This is not to say, of course, that women did not participate in the creation of natural knowledge in different ways. See for example, Schiebinger, "Women of Natural Knowledge", 194. Sarah Hutton, "Science and Natural Philosophy", 389. Nina Rattner Gelbart, "Adjusting the Lens", *Early Modern Women* 11 (Fall 2016), no. 11: 116-127. In addition to Merian, Agnes Block (1629-1704) provides another example of a woman who contributed greatly to the development of natural knowledge. Catherine Powell, "Locating Early Modern Women's Participation in the Public Sphere of Botany: Agnes Block (1629-1704) and Networks in Print", *Early Modern Low Countries* 4 (December 2020), no. 2: 234-258.

Merian could not afford to publish *Metamorphosis* without first raising some funds, which she did by selling advance subscriptions, not an unusual marketing scheme at the time. Kinukawa describes in detail how Merian relied upon her epistolary relationships with the German physician Johann Georg Volkamer and James Petiver to raise interest in her project.⁴¹ As she notes, Merian was more successful in England than in Germany, where there were few takers for the subscription. Thanks to his status as a member of the Royal Society, Petiver was in a position to share early proofs and a draft of Merian's books with other members, which no doubt contributed to the English demand for *Metamorphosis*.⁴²

Petiver placed an advertisement on Merian's behalf in the Society's *Philosophical Transactions* on 31 December 1703:

That Curious Person *Madam Maria Sybilla* (sic) *Merian*, who hath already published two Vollums (sic) in *Quarto*, concerning such Insects and their several changes, which she had observed in Germany and Holland with their lively Figures; being lately returned from Surinam in the West Indies, doth now propose to publish a Curious History of all those Insects, and their transmutations that she hath there observed, which are many and very rare, with their Description and Figures in large Folio on Imperial Paper, containing 60 Tables, curiously performed from her own Designs and Paintings. [...] Such Persons as are willing to Subscribe for a work of this Nature, (which for its Curiosity and Performance very well deserves publick Encouragement) She desires the first Payment may be speedily made to James Petiver Apothecary in Aldersgate Street, London, to whom she hath sent several Tables, and some in Colours, to shew their Curiosity, and how admirably they are engraved, which may be seen by any that desire it. The Work is in great forwardnes (sic) and highly approved of by all that see it.⁴³

⁴¹ T. Kinukawa, "Natural history as entrepreneurship: Maria Sibylla Merian's correspondence with J. G. Volkamer II and James Petiver", *Archives of natural history* 38, Part 2 (2011): 313-327. Etherington believes that Merian was already a popular naturalist by the time she sought to publish *Metamorphosis*, and therefore questions whether Merian's correspondence and relationships with Volkamer and Petiver were quite as impactful as argued by Kinukawa. For the purposes of this essay, I am concerned with the fact of the correspondence, as opposed to the magnitude of its significance. Etherington, *The Flowering of Ecology*, 121.

⁴² Kinukawa, "Natural history as Entrepreneurship", 318-321.

⁴³ The Royal Society, *Philosophical Transactions* 23 (31 December 1703), no. 285 (DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1098/rstl.1702.0069>).

The term *Curious*, in this case, connotes Merian's devotion to the promulgation of empirical knowledge. It derives from the adjective, which denotes "the mental disposition of being careful, assiduous, and inquisitive".⁴⁴ The designation of Merian as a curious person is therefore not, in and of itself, gendered.⁴⁵ Indeed, the masculine and plural forms of the adjective, *Curieux*, were used frequently, during the same period, as an alternative to the noun *liefhebbers*, translated alternatively as virtuoso, amateur, lover of art.⁴⁶ Importantly, "Generally, it is agreed that *liefhebbers* were learned non-professionals whose knowledge of a given subject or practice enabled them to exercise discernment."⁴⁷ The implied gendering (and attendant diminution) of Merian's achievement, however, becomes clear when one compares this advertisement with an account of the book *Paradisus Batavus* by Paul Hermann, the director of the Leiden *Hortus Botanicus*, in the same publication a few years earlier:

The learned and much celebrated Herbalist Dr. Paul Hermans, Author of this Work, whose Name alone is sufficient to recommend it to the ingenious Reader, designed therein to give us the History of such rare and non-descript Plants, as well European as Indian, as were cultivated either in publick Physick-Gardens, or those of private curious Persons, in and about Holland; as we see now accordingly performed. Of some of those he presents us with both Descriptions and Figures, of others with Descriptions only, and of others which had been before described, but not delineated with Figures, referring us for their Descriptions to their first Authors. [...] The author intended a Second and Third Century, for which he had prepared Materials, having caused many more Plants to be drawn by Hand, which are not as yet engraven (sic)...which it were to be desired, some Publick-spirited Persons or Societies would be at the

⁴⁴ Lukas Rieppel, "Museums and Botanical Gardens", in Bernard V. Lightman, *A Companion to the History of Science* (Chichester: Wiley, 2016), 238-251.

⁴⁵ The original uses the word "curieuste" to describe Merian's Surinamese paintings. This is a word that encompasses a wide range of meanings, here associated with the persona of the *liefhebber*, someone who is a devoted amateur and alternatively called an enthusiast, virtuoso, *curieux*, or lover of art. In this context, "curieuste" could mean interesting, amazing, special, strange, rare, wonderful, astonishing, astounding. See *Historische Woordenboeken – Nederlands en Fries*, Instituut voor de Nederlandse Taal: <http://gtb.inl.nl/search/#>. For a lexicographical overview of Dutch seventeenth-century art historical sources that use the expression *liefhebber*: LexArt AdGn°323761 <https://lexart.fr/terms/view/1843>. I am grateful to Dr. Claudia Swan for having provided me with this reference.

⁴⁶ The masculine and the plural forms of the noun "curieux" (a word of French origin) are the same.

⁴⁷ Claudia Swan, "*Liefhebberij*: A Market Sensibility", in Inger Leemans and Anne Goldgar (Eds.), *Early modern knowledge societies as affective economies* (Abingdon; New York: Routledge, 2021), 142. Swan provides an overview of the earlier literature concerning *liefhebbers* and their characteristics.

Charge of cutting in Brass, that so great a Treasure be not wholly suppressed and lost. All that I shall or need say of this Piece is, That the Descriptions are very accurate, and sufficient alone to lead us into a certain and unerring Knowledge of the Plants described, and withal concise, and not encumbered with superfluous and unnecessary Stuff, which obscures rather than illustrates [...] ⁴⁸

The book produced by Hermann, although focused solely on plants, was similar to *Metamorphosis*, consisting of descriptions and illustrations. Both works offered information heretofore unknown regarding exotic specimens. Yet, Merian is a Curious Person, while Hermann is Learned. Hermann's name alone, the reader is told, is sufficient to recommend his book to the ingenious reader. In Merian's case, Petiver suggests that the public should encourage the author for a work so diligently and capably performed. In Hermann's case, the botanist John Ray (author of the account, the same who included Merian in an epilogue to his *Historia Insectorum*, above), suggests that should the public not act to have the drawings commissioned by Hermann (but executed by someone else) engraved, a treasure would be lost. Hermann offers "certain and unerring Knowledge"; Merian offers rare insects admirably engraved and a work "highly approved of" by unnamed persons.

Although Hermann occupied a high-profile position and was formally educated, the type of language used to promote his book *Paradisus Batavus* was also used in cases of lesser known men. For example, James Petiver, in providing an account of a book of East India plants by Samuel Browne, wrote:

The World is very much obliged to Mr. [Samuel Browne] for the certain knowledge of this Tree, which has hitherto lain in Obscurity, we having until now only seen the Fruit in the Shops. ⁴⁹

⁴⁸ The Royal Society, *Philosophical Transactions* 21 (31 December 1699), no. 249: 63-67. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1098/rstl.1699.0012>.

⁴⁹ The Royal Society, *Philosophical Transactions* 22 (31 December 1701), no. 27: 844. <https://royalsocietypublishing.org/doi/pdf/10.1098/rstl.1700.0086>

Antonie van Leeuwenhoek, known for his pioneering work in microscopy, worked primarily in the textile industry and was largely self-taught; he did not write a book, nor did he write in Latin.⁵⁰ Yet, he became a Fellow the Royal Society and his letters were frequently published in the *Philosophical Transactions*. Upon his death, he bequeathed his microscopes and cabinets of curiosities to the Royal Society, which acknowledged his contributions: “Discoveries; they are so numerous as to make up a considerable Part of the *Philosophical Transactions*...And of such Consequence, as to have opened entirely new Scenes in some Parts of Natural Philosophy”.⁵¹

Discoveries; consequence; certain knowledge: none of these terms were applied to Merian or to her work by the formal institutions of natural history or by their members. In fact, her work as a naturalist only featured twice in the *Philosophical Transactions* during the eighteenth century, in addition to the advertisement placed by Petiver: once in reference to a certain type of cockroach that she had identified, and once more when a Fellow of the Society referred to Merian’s description of a “frog-fish” in order to buttress his identification of a slightly different specimen.⁵² Neither Merian nor her work received a mention in the *Mémoires de l’Académie Royale des Sciences*, located in Paris.

Merian’s near-complete absence from the formal institutions of natural history is significant. The *Philosophical Transactions*, in particular, offered an international platform for

⁵⁰ Iain C. Sutcliffe (ed.), “Still Going Strong: Leeuwenhoek at Eighty”, Special Issue: Antonie van Leeuwenhoek, *Journal of Microbiology*, 106 (2014). See also Antonie van Leeuwenhoek and Leeuwenhoek-Commissie, *Alle de brieven van Antoni van Leeuwenhoek = The collected letters of Antoni van Leeuwenhoek*, Part XIV (1701-1704) (Lisse: Swets & Zeitlinger, 1996). Part XV (1704-1707) was published in 1999.

⁵¹ Royal Society, *Philosophical Transactions* 32 (31 December 1723), no. 38: 449. <https://royalsocietypublishing.org/doi/pdf/10.1098/rstl.1722.0090>

⁵² “A few Days before this, a Friend had sent me Three or Four Cock-Roches, or as Merian calls them, Kakkerlaciae, brought alive from the West-Indies...”. The Royal Society, *Philosophical Transactions* 41 (1 January 1740), no. 457: 443. <https://doi.org/10.1098/rstl.1739.0074>. “Mrs. Merian’s Description is as follows...The frogs of Asia and Africa are described by this author, plate 72...” The Royal Society, *Philosophical Transactions* 51 (31 December 1759): 653. <https://royalsocietypublishing.org/doi/pdf/10.1098/rstl.1759.0062>

the discussion and dissemination of natural philosophy and natural knowledge. Inclusion in this publication offered a tacit seal of approval to authors; it legitimized their efforts, hypotheses, and experiments by releasing them into the public sphere of early modern scientific discourse.⁵³

George Cuvier, in setting out what he believed were the key lessons in natural history from the sixteenth and seventeenth centuries, noted: “Together with *Mémoires de l’Académie des Sciences de Paris*, this publication [the *Philosophical Transactions*] is the one that has contributed the most to our knowledge of nature and its various phenomena.”⁵⁴ Merian, notwithstanding the diligence and devotion she brought to her subject, her commitment to empiricism, and her careful observations, remained an outsider. She was admired as a *liefhebber* and as an artist, but was not considered a full participant in the creation and dissemination of natural knowledge, at least not insofar as her masculine professional contemporaries were concerned.

Conclusion

A few years before Merian passed away, she received the visit of the German polymath Zacharias Conrad von Uffenbach. In his travel account, he recalls how he had been moved to visit the artist after having seen her watercolours in the collection of Hans Sloane, in London. Regarding his visit with Merian, Uffenbach recounts her trip to Suriname, which was cut short because Merian could not bear the heat. He continues:

Her only pleasure has been to seek out the beautiful butterflies, plants and other creatures, and to paint them from life. She is [sixty-two] years old, but still quite lively, and a very polite mannerly woman, very artful in watercolours and quite diligent.⁵⁵

⁵³ David Zaret, “Religion, Science, and Printing in the Public Spheres in Seventeenth-Century England”, in Craig Calhoun (ed.), *Habermas and the Public Sphere* (Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 1992), 217-218. Zaret was concerned with early modern England, but his conclusion is equally applicable to the Dutch Republic. On this point, see also Powell, “Locating Early Modern Women”, 247-248.

⁵⁴ Cuvier, *Cuvier’s History of the Natural Sciences*, Chapter 12, paragraph 17.

⁵⁵ Zacharias Conrad von Uffenbach, *Merkwürdige Reisen durch Niedersachsen Holland und Engelland*, vol. 3 (Frankfurt, Leipzig: Christian Ulrich Wagner, 1754): 553.

That he thought it worthwhile to record Merian's disposition is a sign of the fact that as much as he admired her watercolours and observations, Uffenbach could not separate Merian's work from her gender.

Within a few years of the publication of *Metamorphosis*, James Petiver published his own *South-Sea Herbal* (1715). On the first page there appeared a list of "Books, Tracks &c. Published by the Author". That list included "Madam Merian's History of Surinam Insects, abbreviated and methodized, with some Remarks on them". What Petiver telegraphed to his readers was that he had improved Merian's *Metamorphosis*. By naming himself as publisher and including the title as part of a list of his own works, he presumed to give the work a veneer of legitimacy. In 1767, when James Epton published Petiver's entire body of work as *Jacobi Petiveri Opera*, he included a list of plates and tracks "which completes all he ever wrote upon Natural History." Number 112 on that list is Merian's *Surinam Insects*. Within a matter of decades, Merian's masterpiece had been assimilated into the body of work of the only man who had cited her earlier work and even promoted her in the *Philosophical Transactions*.

Increased professionalization and institutionalization accompanied the growth in popularity of natural history during the course of the seventeenth century. Men, quite simply, wished to limit access to the field: relying almost exclusively on the use of Latin and requiring membership in institutions as evidence of *bona fides* fulfilled this objective. Not only were women excluded, but so were members of visible communities and of the lower economic classes. Martha Howell put it best when she remarked, "women might be tolerated in an economic, social or cultural space occupied by men, but if that space was powerful enough to confer honour on men, women were both discursively and in practice marginalized in it."⁵⁶ In

⁵⁶ Martha Howell, "Michaelina Wautier and Working Women in Early-Modern Europe", in Katlijne van der Stighelen, Katlijne et al. (eds.), *Michaelina Wautier, 1604-1689: Glorifying a forgotten talent* (Antwerp: BAI, 2018), 101.

addition to natural history, this practice also applied to arts, culture, and literature. Gendered language was one very effective method of marginalization; the other, deployed by the scientific academies, was omission.

Merian received praise from different strata of society and succeeded in selling books and in shifting the course of natural history, which is more than most early modern women could expect. Her readers, however, were never allowed to forget that she was a woman, engaged in men's work. She was remarkable—for a woman.

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Misogyny in the Boudoir:

How a French Libertine Tale Hijacked Early Modern Women's Literature

Aurora Wolfgang

The satiric and licentious fairy-tale genre that emerged after 1730 in France appropriated the traditional fairytale dominated by late seventeenth-century women writers in order to render ridiculous a whole tradition of French women's narratives. Following in the tradition of satirizing women-centered sociability and literature, in works such as Molière's *Les précieuses ridicules* and Abbé Michel de Pure's *La précieuse*, Jacques Rochette de la Morlière's *Angola, Histoire indienne*¹ serves as a key example of how libertine fairytales worked to de-legitimize women's contributions to literature as a whole. In this essay, we demonstrate how La Morlière's novel deforms the signifiers of women's sociability, asserts masculine power over women, and attacks many fundamental aspects of women's narratives. *Angola* stands as a symptom of the backlash against women's social and literary power in the seventeenth and early eighteenth centuries which, according to Joan DeJean, "created a tear in the fabric of history."² In fact, as Raymonde Robert observes, male-authored satirical and licentious fairytales overtake the traditional model of the fairytale written by women. By 1746, La Morlière's mocking of women's sociability in *Angola* resonated so well with readers that it created a literary sensation.³

We know that seventeenth-century French women authors constructed a trope of sociability in which *salonnières* "governed" knowledge and language within salon culture—a system based on equality and reciprocity.⁴ The trope's origins can be traced to the salons of seventeenth-century women as well as to *Artamène, ou le Grand Cyrus* and *Clélie, Histoire romaine*, the monumental texts of Madeleine de Scudéry, a writer who glorified women's

intellect, conversation, and heroism in her work. Women's participation in *mondaine* and salon culture was attacked progressively throughout the eighteenth century, culminating in Jean-Jacques Rousseau's accusation that social contact within women-led salons emasculated the men of the Republic of Letters.⁵

In addition to the cultural trope of sociability, women fiction writers focused on the physical and emotional freedom of women: Marie-Catherine Desjardins de Villedieu's *Memoirs of the Life of Henriette-Sylvie de Molière (Mémoires de la vie de Henriette-Sylvie de Molière)*⁶ and Gabrielle-Suzanne de Villeneuve's *Beauty and the Beast (La Belle et la Bête)*,⁷ for example, show in very different ways how women can control their own movements and sexuality when faced with the threat of male dominance. From Scudéry to Villeneuve, heroines maneuver through patriarchal obstacles to choose for themselves their romantic partners for marriage or intimacy. By creating fantasy worlds, French women writers legislated the laws and rules that safeguarded their heroines' physical and emotional agency.

Our article will examine the trope of women's *mondaine* sociability in a variety of women's genres as well as the ways in which three successful writers—Scudéry, Villedieu, and Villeneuve—depict women's physical autonomy and emotional integrity in contrast to La Morlière. The libertine satiric mode, exemplified by La Morlière, allows male writers to reassert their masculinity and virility by systematically denigrating the popular women's genres and their reading public. Indeed, certain male writers were intent upon hijacking and replacing the genre that had made women a significant presence in the literary field. The libertine fairytale is one key example of attempts to silence women's voices in literature just as those women found a place in the public sphere.

Women's Fairytales, Men's Satire

In the late seventeenth century, salon women began inventing and publishing fairytales in order to create for themselves “fabulous identities” according to Patricia Hannon.⁸ Indeed, salon women such as Marie-Catherine d’Aulnoy, Marie-Jeanne L’Héritier de Villandon, Henriette-Julie Castelnau de Murat, and Catherine Durand were at the forefront of the creation of the literary fairytale from 1690-1715, to such an extent that the figure of the “fairy” became synonymous with the *salonnière*. Lewis C. Seifert went so far as to call the phenomenon a “rare literary movement dominated by women” as the works of women writers accounted for two-thirds of fairytales published.⁹ Once this generation of fairy-tale writers receded into the past, however, their successful genre was appropriated by male authors writing libertine fiction.¹⁰ Robert notes that between 1734 and 1754, a flurry of seventeen satiric and libertine works was published in the fairy-tale genre.¹¹ *Angola* stands as one such text that aims to attack the women writers and their proto-feminist works that were featured predominantly in the literary field of La Morlière’s day. *Angola* begins with a frame narrative in which a marquis and a countess read an erotic fairytale that mocks the tropes of women’s fiction, such as women’s centrality in mixed-gender sociability and women’s strategies for controlling their affective and erotic choices. A young prince, Angola, is condemned by the fairy, Mutine, to unhappiness in love. Thus, Angola must enter the court of the worldly fairy Lumineuse to receive an explicitly libertine education to prevent him from falling in love. Ultimately, these efforts fail and Mutine’s curse comes true.

In these types of satiric fairytales, as Robert explains, “the inanity and stupidity of the genre they are practicing, was a means for [male writers] to dominate the field in relation to the texts they are parodying and above all to set down new points of reference that will allow the reader to enter into their game and align themselves with their project of derision.”¹² Moreover,

Pierre Blanchard, quoting Pascal Bailly's *La muse indignée*, emphasizes how satire includes a phallic dimension as the male author asserts his virility through his aggressively misogynistic text: "Misogyny and the disdain of women constitute a significant part of the satiric *ethos*, so much so that the opposition between masculinity and femininity becomes one of the fundamental frameworks of satire."¹³ Thus, in La Morlière's tale, satire acts as a destructive modality; Lumineuse's fairy-tale world epitomizes a system that aims to systematically denigrate women.¹⁴ Regarding the *petits-mâîtres* of the court, the coquette Zobéide explains, "it has become fashionable today to have the worst manners toward women, to consider them detestable, and to speak of them in the most outrageous and indecent ways."¹⁵ The fairy queen Lumineuse exists as only the titular head of the salon, whereas men, particularly the libertine Almaïr, make the rules. That is, while her court contains some of the signifiers of the salon (woman at the top, a coterie that admires her, a social/educational/cultural space for polite society), it is distorted. *Angola* presents a libertine universe where the ladies are flirts and all mixed-gender interaction leads to sexual relations.

La Morlière's dedication, "To the Coquettes," begins his mockery of French women readers; literary works had traditionally been addressed "To the Ladies."¹⁶ This designation of respect for women, according to Rousseau, originated in bygone days when men truly found women worthy of respect. However, in the mid-eighteenth century, he writes: "it is no less essential in French gallantry to scorn women than to serve them. This scorn is a sort of authority that impresses them. ... Anyone who would respect [women] would pass for a novice in [women's] eyes, a knight-errant, a man who has known women only in novels."¹⁷ Thus, in Rousseau's view, even women now reject the reverential attitudes found in romance fiction of the previous century. Such will be the lesson of *Angola*, who learns to dispense with his

respectful manners toward women by Almaïr, a *petit-maître*, and replace respect with scorn. Almaïr reminds his pupil “that nothing is so miserable as playing the role of the hero of a novel.”¹⁸

In its Preface, the novel opens on the double register of the *courtois* and the libertine: a young marquis pays a visit to the Countess de S. hoping to be introduced into her *ruelle*, or the space between the bed and wall in which seventeenth-century salon women sometimes held court while recovering from childbirth. The term *ruelle* became intimately associated with women’s salon gatherings. The marquis hopes to find the Countess in bed, not for intellectual repartee, but for seductive banter. They agree to read, and then “discuss,” the latest brochure *Angola, Histoire indienne*, or the book itself, that the Countess has just received. The marquis insists that their party will be a *tête à tête*, and not an “assembly,” transforming what used to be a social and cultural gathering into a sexual one.¹⁹

As it turns out, Angola and Almaïr present two sides of the same coin. Angola initially pleases the women of the court through his respectful deference, while Almaïr, the *petit-maître*, seduces them through his worldly manners and aggressive moves. The *courtois* hero and the *petit-maître* were both considered effeminate in their day for their proximity to women. In fact, Karen J. Mana explains:

The first literary representations of the *petit-maître* [sic] emphasize another one of the character’s emblematic qualities: effeminacy. In the seventeenth century, the term *efféminé* usually described the type of man who liked to frequent women’s spaces (the salon, the boudoir), fixated on them, and exploited them.²⁰

Moreover, impotence was considered the “distinguishing quality” of the *petit-maître*.²¹ Angola and Almaïr are obsessed with enjoying women’s favors, each in their own way, spending time in

the women-dominated spaces of the salon, the *ruelle*, the *cabinet*, and the garden house. Angola is dependent on a woman, Lumineuse, to launch him into and teach him the ways of polite society, while Almaïr seeks to displace Lumineuse as Angola's teacher. Despite their subservience to Lumineuse and their participation in her female court (at least on the surface), they seek to get pleasure from women on their own terms.

From "lady" to "coquette," La Molière demotes the female reading public from women of taste, who perhaps lead their male peers in conversation and literary creation, to flirtatious and permissive socialites, women worthy of "scorn" who read not for knowledge, but for titillation in bed, "after a night spent voluptuously in the arms of an adored lover."²² Thus libertine novels like *Angola* simply rewrite the tropes of French women's literature to enact the male sexual fantasy of social domination and control of women.

Lumineuse the Fairy Queen and her Sex Salon

In the seventeenth and early eighteenth centuries, salons featured both serious and light-hearted discussion²³ concerning politics and literature, and were mixed-gender. Lumineuse's court most resembles seventeenth-century salons in that it is heterosocial and its purpose is not serious.²⁴ In the tradition of Baldesar Castiglione's *The Book of the Courtier* (1528), the French salon was promoted as a school for high-society men in which ladies teach the rules of politeness according to their own pronouncements.²⁵ In this respect, Lumineuse's court functions like a traditional salon gathering led by a prominent woman. The narrator describes it as follows:

She had the most magnificent and the most gallant court of that time. The country's manners set the tone for all the neighboring courts. As for matters of education, they were the most exquisite, and all the foreign princes, happy to be known by the fairy, sent their

children there to receive instruction, then to gain access to the court, and to acquire the worldly airs of the most elite members of society.²⁶

It is useful to understand Lumineuse as a distortion of the *salonnière*. Writers such as La Molière ridiculed such coteries, but, as DeJean suggests, men's derision was due to the social and gender subversion of these salons.²⁷ As in the seventeenth-century salon, the *habitués* of Lumineuse's court seek diversion and avoid *ennui*, not through games and conversation but through sexual adventures, as sexual actors and manipulators. Indeed, Lumineuse's court is a school for libertine education, which is why she offers her court as a place of refuge for Angola, who had been condemned at birth by the fairy Mutine to experience great unhappiness in love. Lumineuse proposes to the king, Angola's father: "All his misfortunes must be based on a serious and tender attachment; my court is the most excellent antidote to this kind of poison."²⁸ Lumineuse takes charge of Angola's "education" herself, in order to guide him past the "pleasant dangers and delightful illusions" at court and disabuse him of the "ludicrous prejudices that fill the pedantic lessons that tutors feed young men."²⁹ Those "ludicrous prejudices" turn out to be the outdated notions of deference and respect for women found in the romance novels of the previous century. Lumineuse tells Angola that, "such an obstinate respect now only exists in *Cassandra*."³⁰

The Erotics of Conversation and Reading

In French women's literature, reading and writing, like conversation, function as forms of amicable and cultural exchange between women and men. Although the signifiers of the salon are present at Lumineuse's court, the ruling principles of the coteries are diametrically opposed. Conversation was the main pedagogical activity of the salon, and its corollary, reading, was presided over by a prominent woman. The celebrated author and salonnière, Madeleine de

Scudéry, for example, made salon conversation central in her writings. Sapho and Clélie, two fictional salon women from Scudéry's novels, reign over a heterosocial, feminocentric circle which is devoted to pleasurable activities. Sapho's authority in her circle does not derive from noble birth but from her intellect, skill, and personal merit: "Her confident manner gives her such a command over others that she can say whatever she wishes to say to those around her and yet always seems to please."³¹ Sapho's role in the coterie has to do with the regulation and control of conversation.³² DeJean notes the anti-narrative aspect of Scudéry's *Clélie*: "action is virtually limited to the displacement from the set for one conversation to the next."³³ Similarly, in the first part of La Morlière's *Angola*, at Lumineuse's court, the action is also fairly limited to the displacement from one sexual encounter to the other. Sex, that is, has the function of conversation. It is important to note that Scudéry's *Clélie* creates a route and a method, explained in the "Map of the Land of Tender" episode, that teaches the members of her group how to regulate affective relationships without straying into the dangerous territory of love.³⁴ La Morlière, on the contrary, imagines a world in which the free exchange of women's bodies by men belies woman's authority.

In *Angola*, places of conversation and serious work, like the *cabinet* and *ruelle*, are used indiscriminately to refer to spaces for sex. Lumineuse invites Angola to read an erotic brochure in her *ruelle*; Zobéide and Angola engage in erotic foreplay in her *cabinet*, "a place of pleasure."³⁵ *Angola* turns the activities of reading into a prelude for sexual activity or an erotic activity in and of itself. The eroticism of reading becomes explicit in an episode involving Angola and Lumineuse. After all guests but Angola have been dismissed and the two are alone together in Lumineuse's private "petits appartements"—rooms that manifest "all the different

degrees of sensual pleasure”³⁶—the fairy explains the pedagogical qualities of a *brochure* that she suggests they read together:

The situations are said to be interesting; the author understands the heart and skillfully handles all its intricacies. Love is treated with delicacy and without muddled jargon; the lover knows how to seize a favorable moment and be made so happy by it that his mistress has neither the time nor the desire to reproach herself for her weakness.

In order to indicate that the text she proposes reading will offer lessons to be applied, Lumineuse opens the *brochure* and states, “Let’s see. . . maybe we will find here a situation or some advice that you will be able to use.”³⁷

Erotic reading practices contrast sharply with those of the woman-centered salons because reading in La Morlière’s novel is both frivolous and leads to sex. As Goodman states, reading aloud in Enlightenment salons provided a forum for young authors: works were read aloud in a kind of first publication, seriously discussed, critiqued and improved.³⁸ In *Angola*, however, the text one reads—both in the frame episode and at Lumineuse’s court—is the *brochure*, a distortion both in length and quality of prose fiction—in other words, the novels that salons produced.³⁹ In *Angola* too, reading *brochures* sets in action the circulation of bodies through sexual activity. In the frame narrative, the marquis and the countess, in order to stimulate erotic desire, read the story of *Angola*, which is described as a *brochure*. Sexual innuendo laces the vocabulary used by the marquis and countess in their discussion. For example, the novel will end with “wand-waving” (*operations de baguette*), says the marquis, in other words, the male phallus will substitute for the fairy’s wand. Also, the countess wonders suggestively whether she and the marquis will be able to “persevere” until the end of reading the novel, thereby doubting their ability not to act upon the sexual titillation of the joint reading. Ultimately, the marquis

hopes that the countess will want to become a *petite-maitresse* or *coquette* (she professes to being their “sworn enemy” in the preface), who becomes sexually available to her *petit-maitre* counterpart.⁴⁰

The Circulation of Women and Women’s Strategies of Resistance

Once Angola has sex with Lumineuse, he enters the general circulation of the court and has sex with several other women; women’s intellectual power is replaced by the allure of the *salonnière*’s body. The “power” of the *petites-maitresses* is to give pleasure to men; however, without being able to inspire men’s love or affection, they hold little sway over their lovers, and simply become interchangeable bodies. Angola recognizes this fact once he feels love for Luzéide; he “understood the difference between the love he was feeling with the passing fancies that had pushed him to take up quickly with all the women in his path.”⁴¹

Lumineuse’s court is dedicated to the sexual exchange of bodies rather than a space of cultural exchange or respect for women. La Morlière’s Lumineuse is an “ageless” fairy who lives in a sexual utopia. At her court, she is an adored sovereign whose subjects wish to please at all costs. The fairy is described as a “*petite-maitresse* by birth and by choice.”⁴² Devoted to sexual pleasure, the court is a space that is seemingly antithetical to violence and conflict: Lumineuse holds the scepter, but her dominance is partially effaced by the familiar way she treats her subjects. While she does not have the power to make men love her (a traditional weakness of the fairy race), Lumineuse does wield sexual power over her (male) subjects. Her *ruelle* is not exclusive at all: given her expertise in seduction, many must have gained admittance to her bedside, like Angola. The women of the court appear to have one thing in common: they

all wish to have sex, particularly with Angola: “there was not one among them that did not desire to pick the first fruits of such a delectable plant.”⁴³

Comments throughout the novel make it clear that the female habituées of Lumineuse’s salon are to be circulated between men. The young marquis of the preface tells the Countess: “at the court, when we’re short of money ... we bet everything, land, carriages, horses, even our wives, if one is willing to accept *that kind of currency*.”⁴⁴ Likewise, the libertine Almaïr describes women as merchandise or objects of mercantile exchange: “To me, pretty women are like merchandise in a shop that may be bought and sold.”⁴⁵

Rejecting these types of misogynist attitudes in their writings, French women writers developed strategies of agency for their heroines to resist the patriarchal system of exchange of women’s bodies. Rather, they insisted upon women placing themselves and their texts under their own control. Indeed, one can read the texts that circulate in women’s fiction as metaphors for women’s bodies. Writing letters and poems can pose a particular danger for women because they can destroy a woman’s reputation if they escape the control of their writers. Letters in particular serve, in women’s writing, as symbols of the precarity of women’s bodies and women’s agency. In *Angola* and other libertine texts, however, the circulation of women’s bodies is portrayed directly and is the primary goal of the male characters. In fact, women characters in this novel are portrayed as complicit in the circulation of their own bodies.

In “The Story of Sapho,” in contrast, the eponymous heroine is understandably reluctant to allow even her friends to read her poetry because this action inevitably leads to the circulation of her work and therefore the loss of its control. Sapho’s most ardent admirer, Phaon, allows his anxiety about her affection to lead him to steal one of her copybooks and, at the same time, to violate the space of her *cabinet*. Phaon becomes jealous when he reads a troubling love poem

and then loses it. Thus, Sapho's poetry is not only read but circulated, causing another suitor, Tisandre, to correctly guess whom Sapho loves. Similarly, in *Clélie*, Lucrece loses any hope of controlling her choice of husband through the loss and unintended circulation of letters that she has written and received.⁴⁶ Thus, for Scudéry, a direct correlation exists between the heroine losing control of who reads her writing, and her ability to shape the message of her story. Most often, this loss results in her inability to make decisions regarding marriage.

Marie-Catherine Desjardins knew the true pain of losing control of her writings: her letters to Villedieu, her lover and intended husband whose name she adopted, were published by him without her consent.⁴⁷ Reminiscent of the unwanted circulation of Sapho's poem and Lucrece's letters, Henriette-Sylvie's letters and those of others circulate in Villedieu's novel and are the source of either diversion or problems for the novel's heroine. Henriette-Sylvie's letters to her suitor D'Englesac also circulate and cause unwanted, embarrassing gossip and even ostracism for the heroine. All of these misdirected utterances (spoken and written) work to counter Henriette-Sylvie's efforts to write and circulate her own story in the way that she wishes. The tenuousness of Henriette-Sylvie's control over her narrative is apparent in Part Five of the novel. While traveling incognito, Henriette-Sylvie hears a competing version of her own story, told to her by Monsieur des Barreaux who recounts a false narrative of her courtship with the count of Tavanès.⁴⁸ As Donna Kuizenga notes, Henriette-Sylvie's consistent message to the unnamed lady ("Your Highness")—to whom the six parts of the novel are addressed—is that Henriette-Sylvie's memoirs—not the gossip spread about her—depict her true life-story and character: "We must replace the false stories of Sylvie's life by these true Memoires."⁴⁹ Here, when Henriette-Sylvie's letters escape her control, she must correct the stories of her unvirtuous

behavior so that she can inherit multiple fortunes left to her by husband and other benefactors, and thus maintain an independent life and agency over her body.

Women's Bodies: Boundaries of Consent

Nancy K. Miller poses the question: “What would a history of sexuality written by women, with women as its subjects, look like?” She reminds us that “what desire means to women themselves is the great question of female-authored novels in *ancien régime* France.”⁵⁰ Indeed, in the literary tradition of French women's novels, we find prominent examples of women choosing self-determination over marriage, despite the intense pressures to do otherwise. Consequently, heroines are empowered to give or withhold their consent as they see fit. Most famously, in her multi-volume *Artamène, ou le grand Cyrus*, Scudéry's alter ego, Sapho, defines marriage as a slavery and resolutely denies Phaon her hand in marriage. Marie-Madeleine de Lafayette's heroine, the Princess of Cleves, rejects passion as a means to her happiness and stubbornly denies the Prince de Nemours his most ardent conquest even when her husband has died, leaving her free to remarry.⁵¹ Françoise de Graffigny published her best-seller *Lettres d'une Péruvienne* (1747), just one year after *Angola*, in which the heroine Zilia insists upon mutual friendship and shared knowledge in place of marriage with her suitor. Each of these heroines finds a commitment to marriage—the institutionalized exchange of women—too steep a price to pay for their freedom. Each finds the strength to resolutely and unwaveringly proclaim “no” to societal expectations.

Even in the fairy-tale mode women make their own choices. For example, in “Beauty and the Beast,” Villeneuve depicts a heroine of impeccable moral character with clear boundaries concerning her physical and emotional desires. In particular, when the Beast inquires if Beauty

desires to share her bed with him, he requires her consent. The Beast tells her: “without fear answer as you must. Say either yes or no.’ Trembling, Beauty replied: ‘No, Beast.’”⁵² Despite Beauty’s fears of retribution, and perhaps even sexual violence, she repeats her refusal nightly. Not until Beauty comes to feel affection and gratitude toward her monstrous benefactor does she consent to marriage, the only acceptable outlet for women’s sexual desires during this period. While this fairytale does end in marriage, Beauty becomes the sovereign whose desires are respected, and for whom the Beast is willing to die. The Beast cannot live without being Beauty’s husband, whereas Beauty makes this sacrifice initially out of a sense of duty and gratitude toward the pitiful Beast. Not until the most powerful women of the tale agree--the Beast’s mother, an Amazon Queen, and Beauty’s aunt, the Lady Fairy who orchestrates the fate of all the characters—can the couple be wed.

Writers like Graffigny and Villeneuve, both inspired by the women novelists and fairytale writers of the seventeenth century, continue a tradition of French women’s fiction in which strong heroines take their own destinies in hand. In the libertine novel, however, women are reduced to willing sexual partners of men, even though *bienséances*, the ever-pervasive social code of conduct, require them to appear to resist men’s advances. The narrator calls their disguised consent “those precious favors that only appear to be forbidden in order to increase their value.”⁵³ Thus, *La Morlière* portrays women’s lack of overt consent as a ploy to whet men’s appetite. The naïve ingenu, Angola, will be taught this lesson by his mentor. When the respectful hero finds himself in an intimate moment with Zobéide, who during a moment of weakness cries out “stop, cruel man ... no, I will never consent. ... Stop, dear lover...” and then faints, Angola dashes to seek help for his mistress.⁵⁴ The narrator explains Angola’s comical error, he is “too ignorant of the ways of the world to know what kind of assistance is appropriate when *ladies*

faint.”⁵⁵ Zobéide’s refusal, however, is part of the ritualized conventions of lovemaking at Lumineuse’s court where “no” means “yes.”⁵⁶

Additionally, even though La Morlière’s heroes are overtly hostile to making love “by degree”⁵⁷—possibly a reference to the Scudérian brand of gradual and graduated progress in courtship—Angola uses a sexualized variation of this method when he has sex with Clénire.

The prince skillfully advanced his plans: he stole a kiss, he placed a hand on an adorable bosom: she chided him, he begged forgiveness for his fault, and a second later he found himself even more guilty. . . . The prince, overcome by his passion, reached *by degree* the keenest pleasure.⁵⁸

The postponement and deferral of the sexual act in this episode is only temporary and enhances the erotic pleasure. However, Angola will come to criticize those “old romances, that chaos of sickeningly sweet twaddle, in which everyone courts by degree, as if in a theology lesson.”⁵⁹

Angola heeds Almaïr’s admonition the next time he encounters a woman’s resistance: during an intimate carriage ride, the fair Aménis tells Angola: “Let me be!”, but this time he flatly refuses: “No, said the prince all aflame, I cannot differ giving you the marks of my love; the truth of my emotion tells me that it is shared and assures me of your tenderness.”⁶⁰ Thus, Angola interprets his own physical desire as an irrefutable sign of his companion’s consent. The narrator’s confirmation of Aménis’ sexual enjoyment during this encounter corroborates the truth of Angola’s assumption, just as Zobéide’s anger for her wasted efforts fainting lets the reader know that the libertine’s perceptions of women’s feigned protestations are accurate. Thus, in the libertine tale, women’s resistance to men’s desire, although feigned, is taken as a necessary and natural provocation to heterosexual sex. Clénire’s resistance is “that charming resistance that brought Angola’s pleasure to its highest degree.”⁶¹

In *Émile or, On Education* (1762), Rousseau theorized women's "slight resistance" to men's sexual advances to be the clever work of nature which allows the weaker sex to provoke men into being the sexual aggressor. At the beginning of book five on "Sophie or Woman" he writes:

The man should be strong and active; the woman should be weak and passive; the man must have both the power and the will; it is enough that the woman should offer little resistance. ... The surest art of arousing [man's] strength is to make it necessary by resistance. Thus, pride comes to the assistance of desire and each exults in the other's victory. This is the origin of attack and defense, of the boldness of one sex and the timidity of the other, and of the shame and modesty with which nature has armed the weak to subjugate the strong.⁶²

Thus, Rousseau turns the common trope of the libertine tale—that women's feigned resistance to men's sexual advances only conceals their true desire to be seduced—into a necessary response created by nature herself to arouse a man's passion while maintaining a woman's modesty, and consequently ensuring that men and women maintain their appropriate sex roles while coupling.

The heroines of the women writers we have examined, in contrast, do not play this game of seduction when they refuse men; rather they affirm their own independence, integrity, and subjectivity in a world which subsumes their personhood into men's. In fact, the heroines of French women's fiction prefer men who are submissive, even impotent, to bring them fulfillment or happiness. The deferential hero, who is often taxed as effeminate by male critics, is portrayed as an ideal companion by women writers. Further, in Scudéry's *Story of Sapho*, female friendship with its qualities of "intimacy, inseparability, devotion, and passion" stands as the model for heterosexual love according to Leonard Hinds.⁶³ And in the Scudérian salon, both men

and women must cede authority to the *salonnière*. Thus, in order to remain close to Sapho, her suitor, Phaon, must agree to never press her on marriage, for marriage reverses the power dynamics between the sexes since “all [men] may become [tyrants] once they become husbands.”⁶⁴ However, following the *courtois* model preferred by women, the mistress commands and the lover obeys. As long as Phaon accepts a nonphysical relationship with Sapho, she allows him to love her tenderly and she loves him tenderly in return. The strength of their bond persuades Phaon to acquiesce to Sapho’s exigencies and to follow her to the female-ruled land of the Sarmatae. Thus, Phaon accepts to be effeminized both figuratively and literally for his lady’s pleasure.

Besides, according to the French women writers, marriage leads to impotence. In the *Mémoires of Henriette-Sylvie de Molière*, Henriette-Sylvie rejects the aggressive suitors seeking to bed her, while she pursues adamantly D’Englesac, the one man whom she loves and desires. After many tribulations she finally marries him, but he proves to be impotent on their wedding night. What might account for the incapacity of this adoring lover? We know that previously, the cross-dressed Henriette-Sylvie had sent D’Englesac to satisfy her female would-be lover in her place. In this way, D’Englesac functions as Henriette-Sylvie’s surrogate; that is, the virile woman with a phallus. While no sexual contact takes place between Henriette-Sylvie and her lady friend, she does experience a pleasant *frisson* at the thought of remaining disguised as the Prince de Salmes and later takes pleasure in enflaming the heart of another woman.⁶⁵ While Henriette-Sylvie and D’Englesac are indeed able to consummate their union, their child dies, rendering their marriage sterile. Thus, while the effeminized D’Englesac does not always physically satisfy Henriette-Sylvie, he is the man for whom she feels the most passion.

In “Beauty and the Beast,” Villeneuve also portrays the perfect hero as a subservient, polite, generous—and perhaps impotent—suitor. Beauty first experiences desire for the “Unknown” suitor whom she encounters in her dreams. Then, the horrid Beast comes to woo Beauty through his kindness, magnanimity, and sacrifice, thereby gaining her consent to marriage. On their wedding night, Beauty’s trepidation turns to relief when the Beast immediately begins to snore, as a sleeping spell has been cast upon him and prevents him from consummating their marriage. Villeneuve uses this moment of male incapacity for Beauty to express openly her desire for the Beast-turned-handsome-prince for the first time. We read that: “being alone, she did not fear scandalizing anyone with the liberties she could take with him. Besides, he was now her husband. Thus, giving free rein to her tender feelings, she kissed him a thousand times.”⁶⁶ Here, male impotence is linked to female pleasure. Further, when the Beast-turned-Prince does awake, he is held in a kind of impotent limbo while the Lady Fairy and the Queen, his mother, debate and negotiate the terms of his marriage. When all the social expectations are negotiated, the couple will be allowed to consummate the marriage.

Notably, in *Angola*, love is the quality which makes a woman special and unique, thus not an interchangeable object in a series of conquests. Angola’s love for Luzéide results in his impotence and prevents his physical union with her: Like the Beast, Angola will succumb to a sleeping spell on his wedding night. The evil genie, Makis, casts this spell for he wishes to marry Angola’s bride, Luzéide. To take revenge, the genie inhabits Angola’s unconscious body to have sex with Luzéide in place of her husband. The next morning Luzéide speaks of her exquisite pleasure from the night’s activities to Angola’s great surprise, for he has no memory of it. Did the sex act actually take place, he wonders? When examining her body, he finds no definitive

answer and no physical trace—no broken hymen, no semen, no pregnancy. All that remains is his wife’s conscious experience of pleasure.

Presumably, this ending is the enactment of the curse by the fairy Mutine that requires Angola to fall in love, be cuckolded, and tormented by doubt.⁶⁷ Angola wonders: Was Luzéide unfaithful? Did Angola’s body actually bring her pleasure, or was it something else—the genie’s prowess, or a fantasy, perhaps? Angola is both emasculated, since he is doomed to fall asleep whenever he becomes aroused by Luzéide, and effeminized, since the genie possesses his body to bed his wife. Ultimately Angola will never know the source of Luzéide’s pleasure that night, but he will nonetheless go on to become her “happy” spouse. This event is equally problematic for Luzéide since she is unknowingly deprived of the ability to consent. Before this moment, she had thwarted all of Makis’ advances and refused his offer of marriage. Thus, was this rape? Neither Angola nor Luzéide can ever know exactly what transpired.

In the end, Mutine’s spell is broken and the world resumes its normal state. Beyond the ending, Angola and his bride will return to his father’s kingdom where one day they will reign as king and queen. The patriarchal order in which the exchange of women assures the proper male lineage will be restored. The court of Lumineuse, as it turns out, is only a transitory space—female-controlled in appearance but appropriated for libertine purposes where men circulate women without any finality, apart from the gratification of their sexual desires. Ultimately, the kingdom and Lumineuse’s court function as complementary patriarchal societies.

What might this ending tell us about the ways in which male writers, such as La Morlière, rewrite the tropes of women’s literature? As we have argued, La Morlière creates a satirized version of the fairy-tale in order to appropriate, demean, and pervert women’s narratives as they appear in various genres, thereby reclaiming the literary field as male. Further, the salon

becomes a space in which men educate other men about how to treat and exchange women. In the libertine mode, women are reified and stripped of their agency so that men can freely exchange them. However, the fact that Angola's bride experiences and remembers her pleasure is a vestige of women's agency. The provenance of Luzéide's pleasure is not determined, but that it exists, demonstrates that La Morlière's narrative is unable to completely strip women of their agency. As in the case of the heroines of Scudéry, Villedieu, and Villeneuve, female characters experience pleasure on their own terms: Scudéry's Sapho, Clélie, and Lucrece feel tenderness; Villedieu's Henriette-Sylvie experiences the pleasurable *frisson* of dressing as a man and potentially seducing a woman; Villeneuve's Beauty feels desire both in her dream of the perfect husband and then eventually with the prince she will marry. Ultimately, like the hapless Angola, what the libertine writer seeks to dominate, he cannot control, and, in the end, while his hero is impotent and unable to perform, women experience pleasure all the same.

Notes

1. Jacques Rochette de La Morlière, *Angola, Histoire indienne*, in *Romans libertins du XVIIIe siècle*, ed. Raymond Trousson (Paris: Laffont, 1993), 355-483.
2. Joan DeJean, *Tender Geographies: Women and the Origins of the Novel in France* (New York: Columbia UP, 1991), 37. For an account of the ways in which women's literature was progressively excluded from literary history despite the popularity of these texts, see DeJean *Tender Geographies*, 159-99.
3. Raymonde Robert, *Le conte de fées littéraire en France de la fin du XVIIe à la fin du XVIIIe siècle* (Nancy: Presses universitaires de Nancy, 1981), 237-38.
4. Dena Goodman, *The Republic of Letters: A Cultural History of the French Enlightenment* (Ithaca: Cornell UP, 1995), 5-6.
5. See Jean-Jacques Rousseau's *Letter to M. d'Alembert on Spectacles* (1758) and *Emile, or On Education*, Book Five (1762).
6. Marie-Catherine Desjardins de Villedieu, *Memoirs of the Life of Henriette-Sylvie de Molière*, ed. and trans. Donna Kuizenga (Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2004).
7. Gabrielle-Suzanne Bardot de Villeneuve, *Beauty and the Beast: The Original Story*, ed. and trans. Aurora Wolfgang (Toronto: Iter Press, 2020).
8. Patricia Hannon, *Fabulous Identities: Women's Fairy Tales in Seventeenth-Century France* (Amsterdam: Rodopi, 1998), 16.

9. Lewis C. Seifert, "On Fairy Tales, Subversion, and Ambiguity: Feminist Approaches to Seventeenth-Century *Contes de fées*," in *Fairy Tales and Feminism: New Approaches*, ed. Donald Haase (Detroit: Wayne State University Press, 2004), 54.
10. Robert, *Le conte de fées littéraire*, 218.
11. *Ibid.*, 237.
12. *Ibid.*, 204. All translations are ours unless otherwise indicated.
13. Pierre Blanchard, "De la querelle des femmes à la guerre des satires," in *Femmes et philosophie des Lumières : De l'imagination à la vie des idées*, ed. Laurence Vanoflen (Paris: Classiques Garnier, 2020), 317.
14. For a recent treatment for the *Querelle des femmes*, see Karen Offen, *The Woman Question in France, 1400-1870* (Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2017).
15. La Morlière, *Angola*, 409.
16. Throughout the seventeenth century, writers of both sexes regularly included dedicatory material to honor their women patrons or readers in the prologues to their works. See Ian Mclean, *Woman Triumphant: Feminism and French Literature, 1610-1652* (Oxford: Clarendon Press, 1977), 202.
17. Jean-Jacques Rousseau, *Julie, ou La Nouvelle Héloïse* (Paris: Garnier-Flammarion, 1967), 198.
18. La Morlière, *Angola*, 442.
19. *Ibid.*, 378.
20. Karen J. Manna, "Sex, Politics, and National Identity: The Petit-Maître in Eighteenth-Century France" (PhD diss., Johns Hopkins University, 2013), 8.
21. *Ibid.*, 136.
22. La Morlière, *Angola*, 373.
23. See Goodman, *The Republic of Letters*, 89.
24. Elizabeth Susan Wahl, *Invisible Relations: Representations of Female Intimacy in the Age of Enlightenment* (Stanford: Stanford UP, 1999), 178.
25. "Men should win favor from their ladies by serving them and pleasing them; but what they consider serving and pleasing to consist in must, I think, be taught by the ladies themselves." Baldesar Castiglione, *The Book of the Courtier*, ed. and trans. George Bull (London: Penguin, 1976), 265.
26. La Morlière, *Angola*, 382.
27. DeJean, *Tender Geographies*, 86.
28. La Morlière, *Angola*, 387.
29. *Ibid.*, 391.
30. Reference to La Calprenède's popular romance (5 volumes 1642-1650). La Morlière, *Angola*, 416.
31. Madeleine de Scudéry, *The Story of Sapho*, ed. and trans. Karen Newman (Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2003), 16.
32. *Ibid.*, 36.
33. DeJean, *Tender Geographies*, 83.
34. For a translation of the "Map of Tender" episode, see Madeleine de Scudéry, *Lucrece and Brutus: Glory in the Land of Tender*, ed. and trans. Sharon Diane Nell (Toronto: Iter Press, 2021 [forthcoming]), 82-95.

35. La Morlière, *Angola*, 409. For La Morlière's use of spaces for sex, see Thomas Kavanagh, "Coupling the Novel: Reading Bodies in La Morlière's *Angola*," *Eighteenth-Century Fiction* 12.-2-3 (January-April 2001), 398.

36. La Morlière, *Angola*, 415.

37. *Ibid.*, 416.

38. Goodman 145-147.

39. See DeJean, *Tender Geographies* 72 and Myriam Maître, *Les Précieuses: Naissance des femmes de lettres en France au XVIIe siècle* (Paris: Champion, 1999), 467. The definition of *brochure* reflects that of the verb *brocher*: it is a fairly short piece of writing, just a few pages, sewn together (as opposed to bound like a book) and written in haste. "Brochure," *Dictionnaire de l'Académie Française*, 4th ed., vol. 1 (Paris: Brunet, 1762), n.p. Moreover, the entry "Brochure" in the Diderot/D'Alembert *Encyclopédie* specifies the term is "most singularly dedicated" to bad books and is a type of literature that makes things circulate: "A *brochure* passes from a woman's toilette into her antechamber, etc., this circulation starts again and draws attention to the merchandise from our mills." "Brochure," Denis Diderot and Jean le Rond d'Alembert, *Encyclopédie, ou dictionnaire raisonné des sciences, des arts et des métiers, etc.*, eds. Robert Morrissey and Glenn Roe (University of Chicago: ARTFL Encyclopédie Project), <http://encyclopedia.uchicago.edu.ezproxy.stedwards.edu> (accessed December 28, 2020), 2.432-33.

40. La Morlière, *Angola*, 378-79.

41. *Ibid.*, 441.

42. *Ibid.*, 386n1. Raymond Trousson explains that *petit-maitre* in the late seventeenth century referred to debauched young lords who shocked society by their dress and disrespectful comportment toward women. *Petite-maitresse* did not come into use until the early eighteenth century.

43. *Ibid.*, 394.

44. *Ibid.*, 377.

45. *Ibid.*, 428.

46. Scudéry, *Lucrece and Brutus*, 223-29.

47. See Donna Kuizenga, introduction, *Memoirs of the Life of Henriette-Sylvie de Molière. A Novel* (Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2004), 6.

48. Villedieu, *Memoirs of the Life of Henriette-Sylvie de Molière*, 166-68.

49. Donna Kuizenga, "'La Lecture d'une si ennuyeuse histoire': Lectures et livres dans les *Mémoires de la vie d'Henriette-Sylvie de Molière*" in *L'Épreuve du lecteur: livres et lectures dans le roman d'ancien régime*, ed. Jan Pelckmans (Louvain: SATOR, 1995), 126.

50. Nancy K. Miller, *French Dressing: Women, Men and Ancien Regime Fiction* (New York: Routledge, 1995), 7.

51. La Morlière sexualizes scenes from Lafayette's *La Princesse de Clèves*. For example, Zobéide "tied bows" (*faisait des nœuds*) while waiting to be seduced by Angola, referring to the scene in which the Princess of Cleves "tied bows" for the Prince de Nemours as a sign of her desire for him (Chapter 9). La Morlière also reinterprets the scene when the Prince de Nemours comes upon the Princess's garden wall from which he watches her at night. In *Angola*, this situation becomes a scene of willing sexual relations after Angola stumbles upon Clénire's garden house where he spies her bathing naked (Chapter 19). For an analysis of the ways in

which La Morlière adapts *La Princesse de Clèves* in *Motifs de retraite, ou Histoire de la marquise de Verville*, see Josephine Grieder, “La Molière’s *Motifs de retraite*: An Eighteenth-Century Metamorphosis of *La Princesse de Clèves*,” *The French Review*, Vol. 51, No. 1 (October 1977), 10-14.

52. Villeneuve, *Beauty and the Beast*, 109.

53. La Morlière, *Angola*, 373.

54. *Ibid.*, 411.

55. *Ibid.*, 411.

56. This convention reflects a general cultural context in *ancien régime* France in which men were expected to be the initiators of sex while women were expected to resist; “violence [was] as an integral element of intimate relations” writes Julie Hardwick in *Sex in an Old Regime City: Young Workers and Intimacy in France, 1660-1789* (Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2020) 69.

57. *Ibid.*, 444-445. For a discussion of the notion of “gradation,” see Michel Delon, “L’idée de gradation chez Crébillon,” in *Songes, illusions, égarements dans les romans de Crébillon*, edited by Jean Sgard (Grenoble: ELLUG Université Stendhal, 1996), 105-18.

58. *Ibid.*, 459 (emphasis original).

59. *Ibid.*, 444.

60. *Ibid.*, 437.

61. *Ibid.*, 459.

62. Rousseau, *Émile ou de l’éducation* (Paris : Flammarion, 1966) 466-67.

63. Leonard Hinds, “Female Friendship as the Foundation of Love in Madeleine de Scudéry’s *Histoire de Sapho*,” *Journal of Homosexuality* 41:3-4, 23.

64. Scudéry, *The Story of Sapho*, 19.

65. Villedieu, *Memoirs of the Life of Henriette-Sylvie de Molière*, 63, 260.

66. Villeneuve, “Beauty and the Beast,” 132.

67. La Morlière, *Angola*, 387.

“What said the reviewers?”: Evaluating Seward’s critical and cultural disappearance in the reviewing press

Francesca Blanch Serrat

Anna Seward’s (1742-1809) career spanned more than thirty years. She held a central position in the literary landscape of the eighteenth century, and her advice and influence were sought after by her contemporaries. Her first publications, *Elegy on Captain Cook* (1780) and *Monody on Major André* (1781) were received with unparalleled enthusiasm by the reviewing press, who prophesied an auspicious future for her. Nevertheless, by the time of her death in 1809, the reviewers’ initial favour had declined, and the publication of the *Poetical Works of Anna Seward* (1810) and *Letters of Anna Seward* (1811) further ratified her critical devaluation. However, Seward claimed that if her verses possessed “the buoyant property of true poetry, their fame will be established in after years” and then, no one would ask “What said the reviewers?” (Seward 1811:4:203). Asking precisely that question, this article will tackle the critical reception of Seward’s works, analysing the variety of androcentric critical processes that interacted with—and were articulated by—Seward’s reception by the press. To do that, this article will examine the evolution of the critical appraisals of Seward’s textual and cultural legacy in the press from 1780 and after her death in 1809.

Keywords: Anna Seward; literary afterlife; age studies; gender studies; reception studies.

Introduction

“Her first publications had been received with unqualified commendation; her youth, her sex, and the freshness of her fame excited an enthusiasm in her favor. These recommendations were of a nature not to last; and every succeeding poem was examined with severer justice and increased impartiality”¹.

In 1811, *The British Review and London Critical Journal* succinctly summarised thus Anna Seward’s tumultuous relationship with the reviewing press, when appraising the posthumously published *Letters of Anna Seward*. Seward’s attitude to the reviewing

profession was one of contempt. Seward often remarked on the critics' role in attributing and discarding merit, and always found them lacking: "can you take a review, or magazine, without meeting criticism on poetry which outrages everything like taste, feeling, or even common-sense?" she wondered in a letter to a friend². She denounced their attitudes as detrimental to the success of contemporary poetry: "yours, yours is all the cloud,/ Gems cannot sparkle in the midnight Gloom"³, and regarded them as antagonists who instead of working with writers to celebrate English literature, hindered them: "how has this age teemed, how does it continue to teem with lyric genius, while those idiots, the critics, shut their eyes on the golden harvest, and call it barrenness."⁴ accusing them of "*betray[ing] the common cause*", of upholding the writers that formed their national literature, "which it is in their *true* interest to *support*"⁵. It is not surprising, then, that Seward's placed her hopes for the posthumous continuation of her literary fame not in the critics but in her works themselves, expressing the wish that if her works possessed "the buoyant property of true poetry", their fame would survive any contemporary attacks promoted by interests unconnected with literary ability, and thus consolidate her name in the annals of literary. In this sense, she wrote that no one would then ask "what said the reviewers?"⁶, and that therefore any public criticism of her poems was written on water.

While the public appraisals to her works were largely positive after her publishing debut, the critics' favour waned as her career advanced. The piece by the *British Review* referenced above highlights this decline in Seward's reputation: "These recommendations were of a nature not to last" they wrote, adding that after 1780, "every succeeding poem was examined with severer justice and increased impartiality"⁷. Indeed, Seward enjoyed a considerable renown in the years succeeding the publication of her first two works—*Elegy on Captain Cook* (1780), and *Monody on Major André* (1781)—, and she was

heralded “th’immortal muse of Britain”, “our British Muse”, and “Queen Muse of Britain”⁸. It comes as a surprise, then, that she all but disappeared from literary criticism during the nineteenth century, her name a curious relic of another time, often in reference to another author but rarely, if ever, of her own merit. However, this article is not primarily concerned with Seward’s critical disappearance—a matter that has already been tackled by Seward scholar Claudia Kairoff⁹—but rather with the androcentric critical processes that interacted with—and were articulated by—Seward’s reception by the reviewing press. Feminist literary theory understands androcentric critical processes as the dominant practices in literary criticism that lead to the exclusion of texts by women from the literary canon¹⁰. These practices systematically consider the male experience as universal and seek to reinforce this universality in literary texts by assigning literary value to it. Feminist literary criticism has made great strides ever since Showalter’s proposition for gynocentric critical practices, adopting an intersectional perspective that highlights and addresses the problematic issues of these foundational texts. The present analysis will focus on the periodical press at the liminal space of the turn of the nineteenth century as perpetrators of these androcentric values by examining Seward’s critical and cultural exclusion from the literary canon—albeit admittedly, they were not the only factor at play—, engaging with the idea, first formulated by Bakhtin and Jauss that “reception plays a formative role in literary history”¹¹.

In the latter half of the century, periodical reviews “functioned as the main site for the establishment of literary authority”¹². The critics Ralph Griffiths and Tobias Smollett are credited as the pioneers of modern literary criticism¹³ for reinventing reviews into a recognisable intellectual genre¹⁴ acting as “meditating elements” between the text and its readers¹⁵, and it was at this time when the critic “emancipated himself into an independent professional”¹⁶. The mode of criticism these reviewers upheld was the one promoted by

Samuel Johnson, based on intellectual authority, human experience and rationality, concepts that at the time were synonymous with masculinity. This professionalisation, then, ran parallel with as a masculinisation of the literary critic and established literary criticism as a site of male and masculine authority, clashing with women critic's voices, who by defending a "feminine" mode of criticism¹⁷ became marginalised. This article will follow a diachronic approach, examining the evolution of the way Seward was portrayed in the press through the reviews of her published works from 1780 to 1804, with a particular focus on the critical appraisals of her posthumous *Poetical Works and Letters* in 1810-11.

Analysis, part I: Contemporary appraisals of Seward's career

Seward's debut publications *Elegy on Captain Cook* (1780) *Monody on Major André* (1781) were unanimously commended for their patriotic themes, and their author was celebrated as one "whose very extraordinary genius entitles her to rank in the highest class of female excellence"¹⁸. These first reviews welcomed Seward to the literary world with open arms, promising her an auspicious future. *The Critical Review* declared Seward "a fine writer, who has a fine glow of fancy" and celebrated her skill for a composition most "elegant and pleasing"¹⁹. The *Monthly Review* foresaw a successful career for the "ingenious authoress" as well; "an Atalanta, if we may judge from her present career, that will not easily be overtaken"²⁰, and considered the *Elegy* an "elegant specimen of poetical abilities", infused with "splendid and original imagery (...) animation and pathos"²¹ and the *Monody* "ingenious" and "singularly beautiful"²². *The Gentleman's Magazine* celebrated the *Elegy* as "embellished with language equally forcible and poetic"²³. A year later, the same periodical would exalt Seward as a "new and splendid star in the female galaxy", prophesying, like the *Monthly* had done, that she would become "one of the most distinguished writers of her age"²⁴. Seward's third work, *Poem to the Memory of Lady*

Miller (1782), was similarly well-received. The critics celebrated that it contained the “same lively glow of imagination, and bewitching harmony of numbers”²⁵ as her first two publications, showing “the brilliancy of her genius, and the correctness of her style”²⁶. The admiration extended beyond the periodicalists, and an amateur critic extolled her as “a poetess of the age, in whom almost every poetical excellence seems to be united. [...] her merit is so universally acknowledged, that I trust I shall not be suspected of flattery even to a female”²⁷.

These first reviews set the basis for Seward’s rise to popularity in the early 1780s. Interestingly, *The Gentleman’s Magazine* credited her father, Thomas Seward, for her abilities, arguing that she had seemed “to inherit the genius, and to justify the arguments, of the author of a *Female Right to Literature*”²⁸. In a biographical account published in the *British Magazine & Review*, Thomas is similarly commended for having “carefully prepare[d] the mind of his infant daughter” and “giv[ing] her a very early and accurate taste for English poetry”²⁹, implying that they his talents were kindled by her father, until her mother Elizabeth, who is said to have “no poetical taste”, “persuaded Mr Seward to acquiesce in such measures as might be necessary to repress it”³⁰. By extolling Thomas and condemning Elizabeth, the press recognises the value of (male) education Seward’s father imparted over the domestic teachings of her mother, presenting her as a deterrent to her daughter’s success. Furthermore, Seward’s ability is phrased through a lens of feminine propriety, described as “unassuming candidate for poetic praise”³¹, underlining an assumed modesty they would later accuse her of lacking, bestowed upon her at that stage as an empty adjective of female praise; and “elegant and pleasing”³². Descriptors such as elegant, pleasing, soft, tender, and graceful were used by the press to refer to inferior art by a female pen, whereas men’s writing would be assessed using words like “hard,” “severe,” and “dignified”³³ to highlight its excellence and prowess. By

articulating their praise in such a genderised manner they effectively split (in a first step towards marginalisation) masculine and feminine as two distinct modes of writing in literary criticism. This is evinced in those revelatory reviews that exalt her as “a star in the female galaxy”³⁴, with an emphasis on the gendered descriptor that celebrates Seward as a female writer, and not as a writer in equal footing with her male contemporaries.

The decline in public favour began with the publication of *Louisa* (1784), which was met with a mixed reception, although it is considered her most popular work and went through a total of five editions. *The Monthly Review* wrote that because of her fame, they had a “prepossession in favour of every production that comes from the pen of so popular a writer”³⁵, but they confessed the poem failed to meet “the degree of excellence which might have been expected from the talents of Miss Seward”³⁶. *The Critical Review* wrote in a similar vein about Seward’s fame, but admitted that *Louisa* was “neither intricate nor marvellous”³⁷. They praise her descriptions³⁸, but remark that some passages written in the style of the trend of sensibility are “reprehensible”³⁹. As Robinson has argued, *Louisa* brings together elements of early eighteenth-century verse epistle with the Romantic epistolary novel⁴⁰, a communion of past and future in which she prizes the poetic expression of her character’s inner turmoil, and it is precisely this that meets with the critics’ reticence. Indeed, all the reviewers protested against the florid expression of the piece: *The Monthly Review* found her expression cumbersome and affected, “ambitious of exhibiting splendid language, rather than speaking the unaffected language of true passion”⁴¹, and *The Gentleman’s Magazine*, in an otherwise glowing review to one of its most frequent contributors, admit to some “inharmonious” lines⁴². Remarkably, in *Louisa* Seward’s focus of attention moves from mourning and extolling patriotic heroes like Cook and André in the guise of the nation’s spokesperson towards a more domestic and mundane theme. And, while the critics admired her poetic “pathetic tenderness”⁴³

and “animation and pathos”⁴⁴ when applied to the first subject, they rejected it in the second. Three years later she returned to the political themes with *Ode on General Elliott’s Return from Gibraltar* (1787). However, as with *Louisa*, this fourth work was not met with the same degree of enthusiasm as her first two. In a surprisingly short review, *The Monthly Review* judges Seward’s verses inaccurately defeatist, and not patriotic enough⁴⁵. *The Critical Review* was similarly underwhelmed: “if the General's own actions do not immortalize him, Miss Seward's present performance will contribute but little towards his Apotheosis”⁴⁶. *The English Review* printed a severe appraisal: “Of bad poets there are various kinds” it begins, concluding that “Miss Seward has always appeared to us a sort of writer inferior to either of these”⁴⁷. They condemn her language as possessing “neither the glitter of the false sublime, nor the inoffensive manner of the prosaic”, and her style as incapable of “simplicity, elegance, and ease”, her imagery shallow and unoriginal⁴⁸. Using an argument that would be later replicated in the reviews for her posthumous works, they claim that Seward “was originally indebted for her reputation to the circumstance of her chusing temporary and popular subjects”,—like Captain Cook and Major André—but “the feeling of surprise is gone”⁴⁹.

The English Review claimed that women writers have “obtained the respectable prerogative of being no longer treated with idle and unmeaning compliment, but of being fairly admitted to the bar of impartial criticism”⁵⁰, and yet they were judging her style, neoclassical in principle and adhering to the trend of sensibility, from a standard that assigned value according to a literary works’ adherence to a modern, masculine poetical mode that rejected both—although it did not break away from the latter but rather redefined and reshaped it—. Indeed, the faults highlighted by the critics in both *Louisa* and *Ode to General Elliott* single out the language of sensibility that made it so popular amongst readers, marking the divide between reading practices and a reviewing press

who acted as mediator between the text and its readership. Seward was caught at a transitional moment in several senses, not only for an increasingly professionalised body of literary critics but also for the trend of sensibility she had read and admired in her youth and which she continued writing in, at a time, the late 1780s, when it was becoming gradually identified with women writers due to its emphasis to bodily sensations and expression, because women were heavily associated to their physicality whereas men were considered intellectual, rational creatures governed by their minds. This gendered opposition grew in the politically motivated split between sensibility and rationality, that identified sensibility with the excesses of the French Revolution and was further ratified by a medical literature of the time⁵¹.

Almost a decade later, Seward published *Llangollen Vale* (1796) and *Original Sonnets* (1799), her last poetical works. Of the first *The British Critic* pointed to its “want of perspicuity, sometimes of sense, and more than one mark of affectation”⁵², and “a fond partiality for particular words and modes of expression inconsistent with the pride and dignity of genius”⁵³, echoing the same complaints regarding the much too affected style and expression already expressed about *Louisa*. The second, however, recovered some of the credit Seward had enjoyed, but none of the warm enthusiasm. As one of the propugator of the female-led sonnet revival, *The Gentleman’s Magazine* deigned the volume as of “undoubted merit”⁵⁴, the *Critical Review* deemed some lines “eminently beautiful”⁵⁵, and *The Monthly Review* called it a “respectable quarto”⁵⁶. The impact of Seward’s pioneering contribution to the sonnet revival has already been convincingly argued⁵⁷ and is beyond the scope of this article, however it is worth observing that Seward’s sonnets were reprinted in collections like George Henderson’s *Petrarca: A Selection of Sonnets from Various Authors* (1803) and Samuel Coleridge’s *Sonnets from Various Authors* (1796). As for Seward’s last publication, *Memoirs of Darwin* (1804), the

critics agreed in considering the biography ineffectual and insufficient. The *Critical* lamented they could not “speak very highly”⁵⁸ of the work. As for style, they consider the language “far from elegant”, in fact it is deemed “involved, confused, and sometimes incorrect”, adding that “she seems to have stiffened it by study, and rendered it harsh by to great anxiety to become profound or comprehensive”⁵⁹. *The British Critic* concedes it will prove “amusing”⁶⁰ for the reader interested in poetry and criticism. They praise Seward’s literary commentary as “sound and good, the result of much poetical taste and feeling”⁶¹. They also find Seward’s prose lacking, filled with “affected and poetical expressions”, and “harsh or extravagant metaphors”, the “very base string of bad writing”⁶². *The Edinburgh Review* coincides with the rest of journals in judging the *Memoirs* “injudicious and fantastic”⁶³, having “been too long accustomed to soar into the high and giddy regions of verse, to be able to tread with sober step”⁶⁴ into biographical prose writing. Unlike the *British Critic*, the *Edinburgh Review* considers the literary criticism inserted in the work “prolix and uninteresting”⁶⁵. *The Monthly Review* highlights Seward’s lexical mistakes⁶⁶, her biographical inaccuracy⁶⁷, and the deficiency of her prose style⁶⁸, dedicating two pages to analyse the defects of the latter, described as “uncommon”, “unhappy”⁶⁹, shocking, “awkward”, and confusing⁷⁰. In terms of content, both the *Critical Review* and the *British Critic* commented on a passage in the book in which Seward argued that Darwin’s *Zoonomia* would be more useful to students than the teachings of Galen and Hippocrates. While Seward always tread carefully when discussing botany for its impropriety from a female pen, she valued the works and defended their usefulness, in the *Memoirs* as in other contexts. However, both periodicals reminded her of her place, agreeing that Seward had stepped “beyond her limits”, with an “injudicious” praise⁷¹, and that it had been said “without knowledge, so also must it be without effect”⁷², reflecting their sexist prejudice⁷³ not only on the propriety of botany as

a subject of study but also on the aspects of education a woman was allowed to comment on public. *Zoonomia* appears to have been out of bounds, and yet Seward challenged this idea and stood her ground.

To sum up, the evolution of the critical reception of Seward's works from her debut in 1780 to her last publication in 1804 was one of steady decline after a very eager welcome. Seeking to identify the androcentric bias in the reviews of Seward's works, this analysis has highlighted the following elements: Firstly, the first reviews celebrate her literary education, crediting her father for her prowess, whereas her domestic education, led by her mother, is portrayed as a deterrent to the same ability. Furthermore, these first encomiums are articulated in terms associated with femininity, establishing a divide between masculine and feminine writing they would only emphasise in the coming years, when the praise turned into condemnation and her language and style were found lacking. This criticism of Seward's poetic style happened at the same time as the trend of sensibility was becoming equated to femininity, and a series of negative traits presented against the intellectual and rational capacity of men. Finally, the reviewers highlighted Seward's subtle challenge to the abstract limits put to the education of women and thus reinforced these same limiting prejudices against the propriety of botany as a subject for women.

Analysis, part II: Contemporary appraisals of Seward's posthumous publications

Seward spent the last twenty years of her life compiling and editing her poetical works and correspondence for publication. Before she died in 1809, she bequeathed these manuscripts to Walter Scott and Archibald Constable, respectively, who eventually published them as *The Poetical Works of Anna Seward* (1810) and *Letters of Anna Seward Written Between the Years 1784 and 1807* (1811). Seward's careful planning for her literary afterlife intended to both "consolidate her literary reputation"⁷⁴ and maintain

control over her career after death⁷⁵, which evinces Seward's unwavering belief in her literary prowess and in the deservingness of her writing, ignoring, or perhaps defying, the critics who had received each of her works with less and less approbation. Perhaps unsurprisingly after the steady decline of the reviewers' favour over her works, these two final compilations met with unanimous rebuff. In this section of the analysis, the reviews to these two posthumous works are examined as a continuation of the decline in the author's critical reception described in part I.

Apart from its redundant rejection of the two works, all of the reviewers fixated on the "vanity" of Seward's publications. This "vanity" encompassed more than one trait the critics judged unsuitable. *The Monthly* suggested the *Letters*, which contained a great deal of literary and political commentary "might have been entitled 'The Opinions of Anna Seward in Various Subjects'"⁷⁶; and referred to the posthumous works as a "triumph of vanity". They affirmed that the posthumous volumes were proof of Seward's "thirst for posthumous reputation"⁷⁷, and criticised Seward for being "vain of her talents", and "pedantic and arrogant in the display of them"⁷⁸. The "vanity" in this first instance, is equated to pedantry and arrogance and found in two faults: being opinionated, in presuming to be deserving of posthumous fame (a judgement reserved tot the critics themselves). The first accusation is tinged with the sociocultural assumption—perpetuated in the moralising conduct books and other types of literature targeting young women—that proper ladies, to use Poovey's term, had to be modest. Indeed, the eighteenth century prized self-effacement in women⁷⁹, and Seward's assertiveness—in the expression of her opinions and in her "thirst for posthumous reputation"—, could be hardly described as self-effacing.

Still on the topic of "vanity", the *Critical* and *The British Review* expressly clarified, in an argument that is reminiscent to that of the *English Review* years before,

that the “vanity” they were referring to was not the one “common to her sex”, as one might surmise, but rather “the vanity of authorship”⁸⁰. This “vanity of authorship” seems to identify something all authors, irregardless of their gender, could be subject to. In a subsequent definition in the entry for “vanity”, Johnson’s *Dictionary* described it as “petty pride” as much as “ostentation, arrogance”⁸¹. I suggest to interrelated interpretations of this pride the critics objected to. Firstly, it is what the *Monthly* criticised, the “thirst for posthumous reputation”: the ostentation of authors “in too confidently anticipating the verdict of later ages”⁸², in believing, as Seward did, and put to paper, that their works possessed literary value enough to ensure their reputation in their literary afterlife, and that their names would be included in the literary annals. It stands to reason that the critics, in their role as mediators between the text and its readership and upholders of the literary values of the moment, considered that it was not the author’s prerogative but their own to grant their favour to the work, by extolling or condemning it in their reviews. In publishing her posthumous works, Seward is bypassing this hierarchy, and therefore undermining their authority. The second interpretation of the vanity of authorship is based on the prejudice attached to autobiographical work throughout the nineteenth century. Writing about the autobiographical genre in the nineteenth century, as the *Letters* could be defined as, James Treadwell has observed that “accusations (or at least mentions) of egotism appear everywhere, attached to autobiographical writing like its shadow”⁸³. The accusation of “vanity” against autobiography was “directed specifically at the character of an author”, in other words, “self-exposure” was considered “a flaw in its author’s moral constitution”⁸⁴. To ensure an autobiographical work’s positive reception, its author must be in possession of indisputable social rank and/or literary ability. At the time, the increase in the number of autobiographies by authors who lacked either eminence or talent—or both—was received as a “sign of decay in the public

sphere”⁸⁵. It is not strange, then, that the critics reacted dismissively to Seward’s authorial assertion in publishing her correspondence and compiled works, as they perceived it as an overstepping of the boundaries of propriety and modesty assigned to her gender, class, and age. Because women were more susceptible to the strict tenets of morality, Seward’s assertion would have appeared to the reviewers as even more violent than a man’s, the arrogance in the suggestion enough to condemn the publications to critical ruin.

Almost two decades after their first publication, in 1844, the critic Robert Chambers still qualified Seward’s “vanity and affectation” as “her besetting sins”, blaming them for having “destroyed equally her poetry and prose”⁸⁶. The mention of “affectation”, is reminiscent of the critiques of Seward’s *Llangollen Vale*⁸⁷ and possibly a reference to her style in the mode of sensibility. In 1785 a contemporary and close acquaintance of Seward, William Hayley, wrote an essay listing the faults of elderly singlewomen in his *Essay on Old Maids*. Hayley portrayed the old maid as a vain creature, “tempted to affect, either such graces as she retains no longer, or such new attractions as she thinks may become her maturer season of life”⁸⁸. As Hayley’s reference reveals, vanity was a flaw particularly attached to women, and especially to elderly singlewomen, who under the appellation of “old maid” were the object of social contempt and derision. These affectations are, according to Hayley, “an affectation of youth, an affectation of a certain censorial importance, and an affectation of extreme sensibility”⁸⁹. The last two, censorial importance and extreme sensibility, were faults the reviewers had indeed denounced in Seward’s works in her later and posthumous career, and it is not surprising, because Seward herself was an old maid. However, while she took pride in the appellation, referring to it as her “‘single blessedness;’ so Shakespeare calls old-maidism”⁹⁰, she was not immune to the consequences her social identity would have to

her reputation. Examining the reviews from the perspective of age studies, placing the identity marker at the centre of our interpretation will further elucidate their androcentric bias.

The social hostility attached to the “old maid” in the eighteenth century singled them out as scapegoats for male chauvinism that concentrated “the denigration and hostility once bestowed verbally on all women”⁹¹. This was a response to “patriarchal anxieties of female economic and social agency”⁹², which considered them to be a “deterrent to national enterprise”⁹³ for have failed in their biological and civic duty to produce sons and daughters for the nation. This placement of value on their role as wives and mothers meant that “the critical transition for female aging was often tied to middle, rather than old age”, the emphasis on “the loss of youth, rather than to the onset of decrepitude”⁹⁴. Critical commentaries of elder women writers’ work reveal just how ingrained in the social consciousness these social prejudices were. Indeed, the confluence of the identity markers of gender and age affected their reception by publishers, critics, and readers alike, and “reviewers used the fact of a woman writer’s old age to dismiss her work’s relevance or quality”⁹⁵, which had a direct effect on their careers and reputations. Reviewers advised these authors a “graceful, polite retirement”⁹⁶ to avoid tarnishing a previously high reputation, because “living to an advanced age may have had a generally negative effect on a woman writer’s posthumous reputation”; although “ceasing publication was not necessarily a winning scenario, either”⁹⁷. Indeed, the critic Samuel Egerton Brydges argued that Seward’s “first publications were her best; and indeed so much superior to her last, as to form a subject of rational wonder”⁹⁸. Similarly, in the “Preface” to the *Poetical Works*, Scott wrote that all of Seward’s productions after 1799 were “unequal to those of her earlier muse”, and that her later poems were incapable “to gratify those whose early admiration has been turned to the original”⁹⁹ which he attributed

to her advancing years: “age was now approaching with its usual attendants, declining health, and the loss of friends”¹⁰⁰ an idea that was echoed by the reviewers. As Seward’s case shows, “aged women writers saw their reputations and fame diminishing before their eyes, and a few”, like Seward herself, “fought to reverse the process”.¹⁰¹ Just like *The Monthly* and Scott, *The British Review* believed Seward’s later writings to be of inferior quality, and described them as “shining absurdities and ambitious faults”¹⁰². In fact, as we saw in the introductory section, they explicitly attribute her early fame to her youth, arguing that reviewers were more lenient towards young women than elderly ones: “Her first publications had been received with unqualified commendation; her youth, her sex, and the freshness of her fame excited an enthusiasm in her favor”¹⁰³. Curiously, the critics refer to this prejudice as common and even logic: “These recommendations were of a nature not to last; and every succeeding poem was examined with severer justice and increased impartiality”¹⁰⁴. Far from acknowledging their sexist and ageist bias, they rationalise this as a natural process: “her powers declined as age advanced” and suggest that “by consulting the ease of her faculties, she would have consulted the interests of her fame”, because “to resign with cheerfulness what if we struggle too long to retain must at length be forfeited with disgrace”¹⁰⁵, recommending that she should have quit when she had the critics in her favour. Not doing so, “she was writing herself out of reputation”¹⁰⁶. By asking Seward to “resign with cheerfulness” her literary career before it has to be “forfeited with disgrace”, the *British Review* is evincing the press’ disregard for elderly women writers, confirming Looser’s assertion that to continue to publish was not an option for many women writers past their youth because it implied the risk of “lowering a once-high reputation”¹⁰⁷. Looser’s interpretation offers a different light to our reading of the critical reception of elderly women writers such as Seward, suggesting that we should examine the critical assessments to these women’s works with a previous

awareness of the effect age had in the way they were received. It also compliments the analysis developed in part I, because the dismissal of Seward's posthumous works is not an abrupt isolated event but rather a continuation of the steady decline they had suffered throughout her maturity and old age: Seward had been progressively pushed aside by the critics for years before her death.

Conclusions

This article has examined the critical reception of Seward's career from her debut in 1780 and until 1711, when the last of her posthumous works was published, in order to identify the androcentric practices in eighteenth century periodical's literary criticism, at a time when the reviewing press established itself as a professional body that mediated between texts and its readers, functioning as upholders of literary authority, promoting and perpetuating the literary values of the moment. The analysis has revealed a series of common elements in the critical reception of Seward's works. The reviews of her first works articulated their praise in terms associated with femininity, linking their value to the author's gender and youth and curtailing the extent of their merit. Seward's style, which had been praised before, became the focus of the critics' rebuff at a time when the language of sensibility became associated to femininity and thus rejected by male writers and critics. Finally, by condemning Seward's challenge to the limits put to the education of women in the realm of botany, the critics embody their role in perpetuating gender roles. Furthermore, the steady decline in the initial favourable critical reception of Seward's works since 1785 culminated with the bleak reviews for the posthumously published *Letters* and *Poetical Works*. The reviewer's fixation on Seward's vanity and the vanity of authorship responds to the contemporary social and moral principles according to which women's self-effacement was valued above all else. By publishing her autobiographical and literary works, Seward asserts her own critical literary authority

and rejects and challenges the critics' authority in matters of literary merit, bypassing the hierarchy in self-proclaiming her literary value. Additionally, contextualising the reviews from the lens of age studies further elucidates the androcentric bias of the reviewers, revealing a connection between the authors' age and the dwindling of their support and evincing how, in the social context of the time, Seward had to navigate a critical landscape that systematically dismissed elderly women's literary attempts.

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Old wives' tales and material metaphors of bad-knowing

Olivia Smith

In 1659 Thomas White asked his reader, if the visions in St Gregory are to be taken as precedents of faith, then 'why may not all *Mettal*-mines be full of departed Ghosts? What *Romances*, what old wives tales may we not expect?'¹ This essay considers the meaning of old wives' tales where they appear as a slur in men's seventeenth century writing. Do we think White is talking about old women and their stories? Nominally it sounds like he is, and St Gregory's vision does centre on a story about a woman who witnessed (with Gregory) a Eucharistic transubstantiation.² But no, White is using old wives' tales to indicate an unsuitable form of evidence. He positions these genres at the gates: ghost stories, old wives' tales, romances, and rhetorically poses the threat of them being let in to the sphere of knowledge he protects. Old wives' tales, like his other two terms, loops back to describe St Gregory himself, and any who have taken his visions seriously. The term enables the argument to take a dramatic walk around the block before returning to land squarely on its first target.

In the twenty first century we inherit the term old wives' tale to mean something like 'superstitious, old story, without scientific or real-world foundations', and the way that this meaning seems to reach backwards through history tempts us to historicise it. We are encouraged to look both for individual old wives and the content of their tales – and yet, in some of the trails laid by the term, we may find neither. Where does old wives' tales indicate a cache of material really derived from women's oral storytelling traditions, and where is it a more detached misogynistic slur? Because of this dual tendency, the history of old wives' tales as a complex term in men's writing often gets blended with the history of women's oral storytelling culture when in some cases they may not fit together simply at all.

First, an analogy. The *Spellbound* exhibition about magic and ritual at the Ashmolean Museum in Oxford comprised three rooms, all curated quite differently (and by different curators). There was a strange tension between the second and third of these spaces which is similar to the tension that exists in old wives' tales. In room two we saw magical objects: doors bearing circular apotropaic marks, shoes and clothes sealed up in walls and chimneys, small charms for personal use – all of which had been excavated and recovered from thresholds and private spaces. Here there was a ladder-like object (called a witches' ladder in the catalogue) which was a series of feathers held together by string, rudimentary dolls and pages of books.³ Room three was very different. It superficially looked as if it was supposed to answer the room two, because its theme was the persecution and punishment of witches. Here were demonising engravings of covens, instruments of trial and torture, the paperwork of accusations, books warning against sorcery. But while the narrative logic of the exhibition space framed the final room as a response to the magical objects in room two, it was obvious that the story didn't hang together straightforwardly at all. The punishments meted out on those who were accused of witchcraft had almost no affinity with the intensely private objects displayed in the previous room. The purposes didn't match up, and nor did the chronology. Although real women were hurt by the activities depicted in room three, it would be unjust to identify the crudely depicted 'witch' figure of the propaganda in room three with the sparsely documented women makers and markers represented by the objects in room two. The actions of those who hid shoes in chimneys, and the actions of those who persecuted women, did not seem to meet on common ground, except on the unstable terrain of a kind of catch-all caricature. Descriptions from one side did not clearly match the actions on the other side, but rather they met in a problematic yet convenient zone of misogynist tropes and gendered slurs.

Some writers who mention old wives' tales superficially seem to criticise women's knowledge, and to target older female storytellers – and other early moderns like John Aubrey actively defend old wives' tales⁴ – but the texts I am concerned with here do not all easily map on to an actual corpus of women's tales and activities, because they are primarily busy performing other acts of criticism. This kind of mismatch is further illustrated by Ian Maclean's 1980 book *The Renaissance Notion of Women*, which as an undergraduate I thought would be a book about real women, but it was not.⁵ Dealing largely with scholastic texts, Maclean instead looked at 'notions' of woman and ideas about what 'woman' meant in writing almost exclusively by men. Maclean wrote about the notion of woman as a component of erudite thought, in the sense that 'woman' could be – to borrow Quentin Skinner's formulation – an *idea* in the context of (in this case mainly men's) arguments. As the examples below will show, old wives' and old wives' tales frequently appear as ideas or notions in seventeenth century writing. Just as the meticulously-documented 'woman' in Maclean's book does not directly map on to the lived experience of early modern womanhood (except obliquely, via the broad cultural impact of highbrow misogyny), the type of old wives' tale I am concerned with has a surprisingly inconsistent investment in real experiences of intergenerational storytelling.⁶

Marina Warner has written about old wives' tales in the gap between these two senses. Old wives and their tales appear in *From the Beast to the Blonde: On Fairy Tales and their Tellers*.⁷ In Warner's account, the tales themselves are 'precarious... poised between wisdom and folly' and she talks about the long history of stories with an old female teller. Although Warner writes across period, going from the Latin old wives' tale – the *aniles fabula* – up to today, her account lingers on the seventeenth century, between George Peele's play of the 1590s, *The Old Wives Tale*, and French fairy stories published at the end of the seventeenth century. Taking up Warner's example, the complexity of old wives' tales starts to show if we look at Peele's title page. It is titled *The Old Wives Tale* which has later been edited variously as *Old wives'* and *old wife's*.⁸ And it is both. The story of the play involves an old wife called Madge telling a story, so it is an old wife's tale (told by an old woman) but also, as it gets told by Peele and the actors of the play, it is an old wives' tale (a second-hand tale). Madge's story becomes a fiction-within-a-fiction as she begins by declaring 'I am content to drive away the time with an old wives' winter tale.' She is an old wife telling an old wives' tale, reiterating it from her own folk knowledge. And yet of course she herself is a fictional character, written by Peele. In this instance we can see how the bagginess of the idea, or the expansiveness of the notion (*pave* Maclean) of old wives' tales operates to highlight and augment the many modalities of Peele's text, from its most interior character to its author. The title of Warner's book highlights perfectly what is at stake: tales are not always the same as their tellers, and a defining feature of old wives' tales is the ease with which they can get into other mouths and minds. Old wives' tales are always already, by definition, moving away from real women referents even as they might be voiced by one: they are in motion, passing on. Warner, and Peele, emphasise the ways in which old wives' tales are so promising for literary writing precisely because of this slippage between real and imaginary targets, and an inbuilt ventriloquising of women's voices. And yet these affordances which are so vivid in a more typically literary text like Peele's seem to slide out of view when we talk about non-fiction prose of the period. Perhaps there is a tendency to take the referential terms of this latter type of writing at face value.

Both Eileen Reeves and Tom Fox have written about old wives' tales as a derogatory cliché and a byword for 'unscientific method'. Fox's chapter on 'Old Wives Tales and Nursery Lore' discusses negative mentions of old wives' tales alongside women's oral storytelling culture, reading one as a critique and attack on the other (while also conceding that they do not directly correlate).⁹ And it is tempting, while encountering this material, to counter accusations against old wives' tales with a celebration and discussion of women's literature. And yet when writers propagate a misogynistic slur this does not automatically mean the closest sounding target should have to answer that slur.

Presenting derogatory mentions of old wives' tales as in communication with women's storytelling cultures may not be fair (and at worse may make us complicit in a sort of 'she made me do it' argument). I want to propose that, in some texts, old wives' tales indicate something more complex in the history of ideas, and should be taken on their own, decoupled terms. This essay considers moments where old wives' tales functions as a fiction in men's texts, a male writer's lore – akin to the kind of thought experiments and stump-stories we find in modern philosophical examples. Misogynistic, yes, in how they use ideas of women's culture as a trojan horse for all they wish to exclude. What happens if we take old wives' tales to be a stand-alone feature of men's literature, their own bogeyman, much like the kinds of superstitious entities these texts would claim that old wives' tales propagate?

1. Biblical inheritance

We see old wives' tales used to draw boundaries in the New Testament, in 1 Timothy 4:7, when Timothy is advised to 'refuse profane and old wives' fables, and exercise thyself unto godliness'.¹⁰

But eschewe thou vncouenable fablis, and elde wymmenus fablis; haunte thi silf to pitee.

Wycliffe Bible (late C14)

But refuse prophane and olde wiues fables, and exercise thy selfe vnto godlinesse.

King James Version (1611)

In these most simple verses punctuation performs what the text wants its readers to do with stories or knowledge marked out as bad. The King James gives us a comma and the Wycliffe a semi colon: a lever pushing the fables away, before turning to the things in the second clause. The poetry of the Wycliffe is particularly generative as instructions to eschew the tales is counterbalanced by 'haunt[ing] thi self to pitee.'

The whole letter to Timothy is concerned with women, and it is from 1 Timothy 2:12 that many of today's arguments against women preachers are drawn ('But I suffer not a woman to teach, nor to usurp authority over the man, but to be in silence'). The following chapter of Timothy is all about widows, and voices a particular suspicion of younger widows. And yet seventeenth-century commentators did not particularly understand the verse to be about real old women. An anonymous text printed in 1689 said that for old wives' fables 'we are, according to learned men, to understand, either the absurd Jewish stories, or some superstitious persons forbidding to marry, and the use of sundry sorts of meats; or those idle and foolish Doctrines which place the worship of God in such low and pittiful things as external sapless Rites, and Ceremonies, Forms, Modes and Gestures'¹¹ and Matthew Poole said it should be read as '[a]ll impertinent discourses'.¹² Historical traces of any first-century women captured in the letter, and the mention of old wives' tales, inhabit different zones in the commentary, and we see early modern readers aware of the generative largeness of the latter – old wives' tales as an expansive purgatory for ideas.

2. Imprints

John Locke's *Essay Concerning Human Understanding* makes use of the way old wives' tales can slide along a scale from the realm of real individuals telling specific stories to general philosophical cyphers. This sliding scale provides him with a useful template for causality when he writes about 'how men commonly come by their principles' (although it may now be customary to read 'men' as 'people' in these sorts of texts, the gendered example Locke uses reflects gender back onto the universalised men/man):

it may come to pass that doctrines that have been derived from no better original, than the Superstition of a Nurse, or the Authority of an old Woman; may, by length of time, and consent of Neighbours, grow up to the dignity of Principles in Religion or Morality.¹³

Locke brings into view this originator-figure, the first tale teller, to show that fixed principles may have accumulated by unreliable processes. Writing and printing are Locke's metaphors, and he highlights the need to be particularly careful with children, who will easily retain impressions 'as white paper will receive any characters.'¹⁴ In this image scheme, false principles would be like a printing error in an early edition of Shakespeare that has come to be accepted as part of a fixed text. An old wives' tale appears in *Some Thoughts Concerning Education*, which started as a letter to a friend about how best to raise children:

But even then, and always whilst he is young, be sure to preserve his tender mind from all impressions and notions of *spirits* and *goblins*, or any fearful apprehensions in the dark. This he will be in danger of from the indiscretion of servants, whose usual method is to awe children, and keep them in subjection, by telling them of *raw-head* and *bloody-bones*, and such other names as carry with them the ideas of something terrible and hurtful, which they have reason to be afraid of when alone, especially in the dark.¹⁵

These bugbears Locke mentions have a long history: the *OED* traces *raw-head* and *bloody-bones* back to 1548, and onward to James Joyce's *Ulysses*. Locke's psychology, in which the understanding is shaped by experience, involves protecting the mind against such frights, and as such he delineates a kind of cognition which is superficially pitted against ideas of old wives' tales despite all the while using them as a tool to think with. The figure of the 'servant' (or implied old wife) permits these spirits and goblins to inhabit *his* text.

3. Stuff and stuffing

Lancelot Andrewes' *The Pattern of Catechistical Doctrine* (1650) is also a book that foregrounds children and pedagogy: catechism is how children acquire the right principles of faith. Old wives' tales make an appearance in the second of Andrewes' seven reasons why Islam is 'false', and he discounts the literary integrity of the Quran by introducing our now-familiar figure:

If ever there were book stuff with those which are called *Aniles fabulae*, old wives tales, it is their Alcaron, which is every where fraught with most ridiculous untruths. *Andreas Maurus*, a Saracen, and a Bishop quoteth nine hundred untruthes in it, whereof two are in one Section. 1. That the Virgin *Mary* was sister to *Moses*, and 2. That *Abraham* was the son of *Lazarus* the Begger, neither of them being contemporary by many hundreds of years.¹⁶

The pseudonymous *Mercurius Hibernicus* used a similar image in the anti-Catholic *A paquet of popish delusions* (1681), writing against a miracle from Bede (which the text calls a 'delusion'):

BEda (whose writing are stuffed with old Wives tales) informs us, that upon a time, a great part of the City of *Canterbury* being on fire, That the then Arch-bishop, *viz. Melitus* commanded, that they should bear him against the greatest fury thereof; and that whereas before it could not be quenched by the great labour of the People, yet at his only presence, together with Holy-water, the fire immediately went out¹⁷

A packet/‘paquet’ is a parcel or bundle of loose things rather than a pamphlet or book, something that is perhaps materially incoherent, but also a wrapper in which things are packaged to be sent (‘a paquet of letters’) or sold.¹⁸ The accusation is levelled at the literature: it is the ‘book’ and the ‘writing’ that are stuffed with incorrect ideas, but moreover undesirable, uncontrolled and even repugnant material (and ‘stuff’, as a verb or noun, is emphatically material). These texts depict old wives’ tales distending and bloating the codex.

4. Bad milk

Francis Bacon altered the motif again when he used old wives’ tales as an exclusionary category in his plans for a natural history. Bacon here is talking about how to set up philosophy so that a great stock or store of it could be amassed and for the need to clarify what will be included from the start.

In the third place, we must also get rid of superstitious stories (I do not say stories of prodigies, where the record seems reliable and likely, but superstitious stories) and the experiments of ceremonial magic. For we do not want the babyhood of philosophy, to which natural history gives the first milk, to get used to swallowing old wives’ tales [...] we do a great deal of good in ridding natural history of the three superfluities spoken of, which would otherwise stuff volumes.¹⁹

Bacon originally wrote in Latin and ‘Impleturæ’ is translated as stuff (v.) here. Philosophy is depicted as a baby who needs to not be fed old wives’ tales *from* the breast of natural history while it (as per the metaphor) feeds. This text takes on ideas about wet nurses and breastfeeding, and of the tendencies of the nurse to affect the nursling – such as we will later see in Jane Sharp’s *The Midwives’ Book* (1671)²⁰ – and uses them to form the rationale for a collection of knowledge. Many of these writers are concerned with how traditions or habits of thought start, and Bacon is talking specifically about taste, and developing a bad taste for the wrong kind of information. This time, nascent Natural Philosophy is the child who is vulnerable to false principles and bad ideas. Imagery of other, adjacent misogynies is collaged together here to characterize a type of ‘outside’ knowledge, even though old wives were unlikely to be wet nurses and the picture hangs together awkwardly.

5. Haut-goût

A conference at the French Academy in the early 1660s considered ‘Fables and fictions, and whether their conveniences or inconveniences be greater?’, and there seems to have been a disagreement over the worth of old wives’ tales. One speaker condemned old wives’ tales that were devoid of truth, invoking putative Lockean ideas of dangerous imprinting on children.²¹ But a different speaker seems to identify old wives’ tales as useful for reviving the weary understanding:

[It] is recover’d by feeding on some dish excellently well-order’d, such as by its haut-gousts, and picquancy will rather excite, then satisfie the Appetite. Such is the bitterness of the Olive, Vinegar in Sallets, and the like; which have the same effect as the stepping back of such as leap, or the appearance of a Fly on a face of an exquisitely fair complexion.²²

In this iteration old wives’ tales are almost complementary, as they pull against the direction of intellectual travel and truth-seeking like a counterweight. Flies, or mouches, were early modern cosmetic enhancements: beauty spots made out of silk or taffeta that could be stuck to the face, either to hide a blemish or to make a contrast with pale skin. John Lyly wrote about this dynamic in 1578: ‘in all perfect shapes, a blemish bringeth rather a liking every way to the eyes, than a loathing any way to the mind. Venus had her mole in her cheek which made her more amiable.’²³

This second speaker seems interested in the satisfaction, re-engagement and interest of the listener/reader, and his theorization of the cognitive use of old wives' tales (they may help those who are 'out of humour with an over-earnestness of study') provides an interesting counterpoint to some of the discussions we have seen. He attributes a different level of worth to old wives' tales but, like Locke, uses them to scrutinize cognitive processes. Although the idea of *haut-goût* encourages the inclusion of old wives' tales it still establishes them as clearly other – opposite, even – just on aesthetic rather than moral grounds.

6. Apocrypha

It is not surprising that old wives' tales appear at moments where early modern texts broach topics of liminality, and ideas that were under intense scrutiny, like the idea of purgatory. John Donne's sermon no.6, preached at St Paul's in 1626, exposes more about the literary stakes of old wives' tales:

the first mention of Purgatory amongst Christians hath this double ill lucke, that first it is in a Booke which no side beleeves, the Booke called *Pastor*, whose Author is said to be *Hermes*, and he fancied to be *S. Paul's* Disciple; And then that which is said of Purgatory in that Booke, is put into an old womans mouth, and so made an old wives tale; she tels that she had a vision, of stones falling from a towre, and then mended after they were fallen, and laid in the building againe: And this Towre must be the Church, and these fallen stones must be soules in Purgatory, and then they must be made fit to be places in the uppermost part of the building, and in the Triumphant Church.

But to consider this plant in better grounds, then Philosophers, or Poets, or old wives tales, or suppositious books, among men of more weight and gravity...²⁴

In Hermas' book of the Shepherd (or Pastor) an old woman tells a story about stones being used to make a building, in which some of the stones sit out the days of their sins in a way that suggests a kind of purgatory. What Donne says is that this piece of purgatory evidence is blighted by 'double ill lucke' – firstly because Hermas is a second century text and not canonical, and secondly because of an untrustworthy narrator. Donne gives a very close reading of how old wives' tales are made: the story is 'put into an old womans mouth'. It is worth noting that the old wives' tale Donne has on the one hand objected to is now in *his* mouth, being sounded out in old St Paul's. The idea of the stones falling down and being remade is a strong one, and in retelling it Donne knowingly supplies a set of imagery for thinking about purgatory even while he says he wants us to reject it. He acknowledges the rhetorical value of old wives' tales, showing his audience how the text converts ideas between different categories of voice and authority.

7. Spectres

In a remarkable exchange of letters between Baruch Spinoza and Hugo Boxel about the question of whether ghosts exist, old wives make another appearance. Boxel writes to suggest to Spinoza that ghosts *do* exist. His argument is that there have been so many stories of them, from antiquity onwards, that something must be the cause. In his reply, Spinoza asks Boxel to send him texts that back up his argument: 'of the many stories you've read about ghosts, you choose, please, one or two which are least subject to doubt, and which most clearly prove that there are spectres'.²⁵ In a longer discussion of his position, Spinoza notes that ghost stories have 'no witness than the people telling them', so that they can 'add or omit details at seems best to them'.²⁶

Although the exchange ostensibly hinges on the evidence of famous authors, the discussion contains some interesting unnamed women: one of Boxel's pieces of evidence is the testimony of his friend who has heard ghosts in his mother's brewery. In addition to this, Boxel suggests that

there may be ghosts but just no female ghosts. On these two points, Spinoza is particularly scornful. These peripheral gendered details coalesce around his main refutation of the textual evidence, and pre-empt the appearance of old wives' tales in his letter:

As for ghosts or spirits, I have not yet heard any intelligible property of theirs, but only imaginations which no one can grasp. When you say that ghosts or spirits here below—I follow your style, although I don't know that matter here below is worth less than that above—consist of a very thin, rarefied and fine substance, you seem to be talking about spiders' webs, air, or vapors. To say they're invisible is to say what they are not, not what they are—unless perhaps you mean that they make themselves now visible, now invisible, as they please, and that the imagination will find no difficulty in these things, as also in other impossibilities.

To me the authority of Plato, Aristotle, and Socrates is not worth much. I would have been amazed if you had mentioned Epicurus, Democritus, Lucretius, or any of the Atomists, or defenders of invisible particles. But it's no wonder that the people who invented occult qualities, intentional species, substantial forms, and a thousand other trifles contrived ghosts and spirits, and believed old wives' tales, to lessen the authority of Democritus, whose good reputation they so envied that they had all his books burned, which he had published with such great praise.²⁷

The idea of old wives' tales is here used as a sorting mechanism for the authority of other writers. Like Spinoza, Hobbes writes in *Leviathan* that old wives' tales are a kind of story that tries to bring about things that aren't there. He writes in his section on the four causes of spiritual darkness about the 'Daemonology of the Heathen Poets, that is to say, their fabulous Doctrine concerning Daemons, which are but Idols, or Phantasms of the braine, without any reall nature of their own, distinct from human fancy; such as are dead mens Ghosts, and Fairies, and other matter of old Wives tales'.²⁸ Spinoza and Hobbes both use old wives' tales to fuse a sense of knowledge which has no grounding with refutations of ghosts being real. In their terms old wives' tales make something out of nothing. In their presentation of old wives' tales several of these writers imagine a powerful kind of literary influence and agency: they depict a kind of snowballing memento, an unstoppable and limitless proliferation, an automated un-thinking that is inert but replicating.

Conclusion

Looking at these texts that mention old wives' tales, do we get the sense of real women as the targets of critique or not? This is a complicated question. On the one hand, these examples highlight how widespread derogations of gendered storytelling were (the texts I have mentioned are only the tip of an iceberg). Many of the examples above draw on ancillary, more tangible misogynies aligned with wet nursing, servants, widowhood, and women's testimony, with which they create a cloud of suspicion into which is placed a mention of old wives' tales. And, as historians have meticulously detailed, this sort of learned writing overlaps with women's oral storytelling traditions in myriad fascinating ways. On the other hand, these texts purposefully hone the idea of old wives' tales as a sort of rhetorical figure that can be filled with other things. It is used to performatively exclude all sorts of material from acceptable zones of knowledge – a more complex, gendered second cousin of the straw man. Writers often use the term 'old wives' tale' to mention and sound out material they don't want to take ownership of, and in moments of epistemic policing. The contents of an old wives' tale can be highly variable: whatever needs to be discredited in the present argument. More than that, they are instrumental in thought experiments about custom and habit. Characterised as highly transmissible and irrational, they are constructed to provide the quintessential counter-example to a particular kind of early modern hard-won accuracy. Often, the notion of old wives' tales is brought in to discredit an idea or piece of writing using complex material metaphors, the seventeenth century version of Mary Douglas's 'matter out

of place'.²⁹ Plenty of references to old wives' tales in the early modern period *do* map onto and interact with women's literary culture, but this essay has drawn attention to this other type of textual misogyny, where old wives' tales exist in the empty container of their name only, in a terrain that is otherwise like Ernest Hemingway's *Men Without Women*, with women on the mediated peripheries, if at all.

¹ Thomas White (writing as 'Albius' and 'Blackwoe'), *The Middle State of Souls from the Hour of Death to the Day of Judgment* (London, 1659). This key term becomes part of the response to White's text – and in his *Mr Blacklow's Reply to Dr. [George] Layburn's Pamphlet Against Him* (London, 1660), p.26: 'The next calumny of the Doctors was his affirming, without limitation, or restriction, that *Mr. Blacklow says, Visions are old wives tales*'.

² Kathryn M Rudy, 'The Mass of St Gregory, the Man of Sorrows, and Prayers for the Arma Christi' in *Rubrics, Images and Indulgences in late Medieval Netherlandish Manuscripts* (Brill, 2017), pp. 101–136

³ For more information on the exhibition see Sophie Page et al, *Spellbound: Magic, Ritual and Witchcraft* (Oxford: Ashmolean Museum, 2018).

⁴ See Aubrey's whole practice of collecting lore, but also specifically his comments in MS Landsdowne 231. I am grateful to Kate Bennett for a copy of this document.

⁵ Ian Maclean, *The Renaissance Notion of Woman* (Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 1980).

⁶ For an account of the historical ways in which women's traditional oral culture intersected with print and men's writing, see Adam Fox, *Oral and Literate Culture in England, 1500-1700* (Oxford: OUP, 2000).

⁷ Marina Warner, *From the Beast to the Blonde: On Fairy Tales and Their Tellers* (London: Vintage, 1995)

⁸ George Peele, *The Old Wives' Tale* (London: John Danter, 1595)

⁹ Reeves, *Ibid.* Fox, *Ibid.*: 'In the [sic] early modern England, female culture was considered trivial and erroneous and at worst dangerous and corrupting.'

¹⁰ King James Bible (Cambridge: Chadwyck Healey, 1996).

¹¹ Anonymous, *Casuistical Morning Exercises* (London, 1689).

¹² Matthew Poole, *Annotations Upon the Holy Bible* (London, 1685).

¹³ John Locke, *An Essay Concerning Human Understanding*, ed. Peter H. Nidditch (Oxford: Clarendon Press, 1975).

¹⁴ Samuel Ward also brings old wives tales into a fascinating 1640 discussion of error, spiritual and navigational, in terms of the lode-stone. With the lode-stone, a person will be able to distinguish North 'even in the darkest night, and most cloudy skie.' Navigating through obscurity without a lode-stone is like moral navigation without the revelation of gospel, and Ward refers to II Thessalonians II in which God sends down a 'deceiving power' so that the people will believe 'lyes, old wives tales, and foolish dreams of Monks,' which become 'rooten Traditions [and] leaden Legends' until they fall, 'blind leading the blind ... into the bottomlesse pit of errorrs'. Ward, *The wonders of the load-stone* (1640) p.30.

¹⁵ The passage continues: 'This must be carefully prevented: for though by this foolish way, they may keep them from little faults, yet the remedy is much worse than the disease; and there are stamped upon their imaginations ideas that follow them with terror and affrightment. Such *bug-*

bear thoughts once got into the tender minds of children, and being set on with a strong impression from the dread that accompanies such apprehensions, sink deep, and fasten themselves so as not easily, if ever, to be got out again; and whilst they are there, frequently haunt them with strange visions, making children dastards when alone, and afraid of their shadows and darkness all their lives after.’ Locke, *Some Thoughts Concerning Education*, § 138.

¹⁶ Lancelot Andrewes, *A Pattern of Catechisticall Doctrine* (London: William Garret, 1641)

¹⁷ Mercurius Hibernicus, *A Paquet of Popish Delusions* (London: L. Curtiss, 1681)

¹⁸ OED ‘packet’ n.1.a.

¹⁹ The Latin original: ‘Tertiò, missa planè facienda sunt omnes Narrationes Superstitiosa (non dico Prodigiosa, vbi Memoria earum reperietur fida & probabilis, sed Superstitiosæ) & Experimenta Mafia Ceremonialis. Nolumus enim Philosophia Infantium, cui Historia Naturalis primam prabet Mammam, Fabulis anilibus assuescere [...] Neque nil, aut parùm actum est, in exonerandâ Historia Naturali Tribus his (quæ diximus) rebus superfluis, quæ aliàs Volumina impleturæ fuissent.’ *Parasceve ad historian natvralem, et experimentalem / A Preparative to a Natural and Experimental History* (1620) in *The Oxford Francis Bacon*, ed. Graham Rees (Vol XI), p. 457 (Oxford: Clarendon Press, 2007)

²⁰ Jane Sharp, *The Midwives’ Book* (London, 1671), chapter V ‘how to chuse a nurse’.

²¹ My quotation is taken from a seventeenth century English translation: Bureau d’adresse et de recontre, *Another collection of philosophical conferences of the French virtuosi*, trans. G. Havers and J. Davies (London, 1665), pp.413-4.

²² The original French of the above passage is interesting for comparison. Bureau d’adresse (1665): ‘Telle est l’amertume de l’olive, le viniagre des salades & le poivre des ragouts, qui ont le mesme esst que le reculer aux Sauters, ou la Mouche auprès de la blancheur du visage. Ces fables sont inuentées pour remettre l’entendement fatigué en sa premiere recherche de la verité, de la mesme façon qu’un fruit enueloppé donne plus d’enuie de le voir que s’il estoit decouvert. Elles sont deux sortes. A scauoir une simlpe fiction, tels que sont les contes des vielles, que ne meritent le nom faluleux...’

²³ John Lyly, *The Anatomy of Wit*. Also see Karen Hearn, *Revising the Visage: Patches and Beauty Spots in Seventeenth-Century British and Dutch Painted Portraits*, in *Huntington Library Quarterly*, Vol. 78, No. 4 (Winter 2015), pp. 809-823.

²⁴ John Donne, *Sermons Preached at St Paul’s Cathedral, 1626*, ed. Mary Ann Lund (Oxford: OUP, 2017)

²⁵ Baruch Spinoza to Hugo Boxel, The Hague, 16–20 September 1674 in Spinoza, *Collected Works*, ed. Edwin Curley (Princeton, NJ: PUP, 2016), vol II (=Letters, 42–84, 1671–1676), #52. See also Gunther Coppens, ‘Spinoza and Boxel: A Ghost Story’ in *Revue de Métaphysique et de Morale* 41:1 (2004), pp 59-72.

²⁶ Ibid.

²⁷ Spinoza to Boxel, The Hague, October/November 1674, #56.

²⁸ Thomas Hobbes, *Leviathan* (Cambridge: CUP, 1996), p.418.

²⁹ Mary Douglas, *Purity and Danger: An Analysis of Concepts of Pollution and Taboo* (London: Routledge and Kegan Paul, 1966)